

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP

PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE 6.1

REGULATION POLICY DRIVING CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
1	31-7-2025	Final report	Maggi E., Porporato A.M., Scacchi M., Gandino A.

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The transition towards a circular economy (CE) represents a key strategy for achieving sustainability, reducing environmental impacts, and fostering economic resilience. Regulatory frameworks play a fundamental role in shaping this transition, influencing resource management, waste reduction strategies, and the adoption of circular business models. However, the effectiveness and implementation of these regulatory mechanisms vary significantly across different policy levels, industrial sectors, and national contexts.

This report is developed within the framework of Task 6.1 of Research Module 6 (RM6) in the NODES project, which aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of how regulatory policies impact the adoption of circular economy principles. RM6 serves as the final step in the technical, operational, and economic cycle of the GRIP project, integrating tools, methods, and processes to support the transformation of industrial ecosystems towards circularity. Specifically, this report investigates the role of existing regulatory policies at the European, national, and local levels in accelerating the transition to a circular economy, identifying key legislative drivers, potential barriers, and gaps in policy implementation.

A core objective of the report is to assess how regulations facilitate or hinder industrial symbiosis and the circular use of materials, particularly in sectors that are central to the NODES project. The study explores policies that govern waste management, extended producer responsibility (EPR), end-of-waste criteria, and minimum environmental criteria (CAM) within the Green Public Procurement (GPP) framework. By evaluating the economic, environmental, and social impacts of these policies, the report provides insights into how businesses can align with regulatory frameworks while maximizing circularity and sustainability.

Furthermore, the report aims to support policymakers by identifying best practices and developing guidelines for an effective regulatory framework that enhances circular economy adoption. By analysing successful case studies across different countries and sectors, this study will offer strategic recommendations for improving policy design and implementation. These insights will contribute to RM6's broader goal of establishing a structured, interactive system to promote circularity, foster industrial collaboration, and facilitate the integration of regulatory policies into business models and innovation pathways.

Ultimately, this report serves as a guidance tool for policymakers, businesses, and other stakeholders, ensuring that regulatory frameworks evolve to effectively support the transition to a circular and climate-neutral economy, in line with the objectives of the NODES project and the European Green Deal. It concludes with a set of guidelines designed to enable this transition, emphasizing the removal of persistent economic barriers through improved access to finance, support for economies of scale, and stronger market demand for circular products. The guidelines also call for incentive schemes that are accessible, predictable, and outcome-oriented, alongside

regulatory frameworks that provide clarity, long-term certainty, and foster collaboration between public and private actors.

AIM OF THE REPORT

The aim of this report is to analyse the role of regulatory and economic frameworks in accelerating the transition towards a circular and climate-neutral economy, with a particular focus on their effectiveness in driving green innovation across different industries. Developed within Task 6.1 of Research Module 6 (RM6) of the NODES project, the study contributes to the overarching goal of NODES to support sustainable industrial development by providing actionable knowledge and policy guidance.

Building on the objectives set out in the GRIP framework, the report seeks to understand how regulation and policy can accelerate the green transition of industries while promoting product and process innovations that deliver economic, environmental, and social sustainability. It examines how regulatory frameworks at different administrative levels—European, national, and regional—shape the adoption of circular practices, with reference to key instruments such as the EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/CE), Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), carbon pricing mechanisms, waste and recycling policies, and innovation policies such as patent regimes.

The analysis proceeds in three main steps. First, it collects and systematizes information on existing environmental and innovation policies, including fiscal instruments, market-based measures, and sector-specific regulatory schemes. Second, it evaluates their effectiveness in terms of economic viability, environmental impact, and social benefits, combining insights from the literature with evidence from stakeholders and case studies in sectors such as textiles and construction. Third, it translates these findings into guidelines for policymakers, aimed at designing regulatory frameworks that are clear, stable, and capable of de-risking circular investments while fostering collaboration between public and private actors.

Ultimately, the report positions itself as a practical guidance tool for policymakers, businesses, and stakeholders engaged in the circular transition. In line with the objectives of NODES and the European Green Deal, it emphasizes the importance of removing economic barriers, strengthening demand for circular products, and designing incentive schemes and regulatory frameworks that are accessible, predictable, and outcome-oriented. By aligning regulatory clarity with targeted economic support, the report contributes to shaping an enabling environment where circular business models can thrive, unlocking innovation, competitiveness, and resilience for Europe's sustainable future.

2. INTRODUCTION AND NORMATIVE BACKGROUND

2.1 CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND THE GREEN TRANSITION

The transition towards a circular economy (CE) represents a fundamental shift in how societies conceive of growth, value creation, and the relationship between economic systems and the environment. The circular economy is defined as a regenerative system that minimizes resource input, waste, emissions, and energy leakage by slowing, closing, and narrowing material and energy loops. It proposes an alternative to the linear economy, which has dominated industrial development by following a take-make-dispose logic, and seeks instead to extend the lifecycle of products through strategies such as reuse, repair, remanufacturing, and recycling. In doing so, the CE plays a pivotal role in achieving a more sustainable and resilient economy and is widely acknowledged as a key pillar of the green transition.

The legal and policy frameworks driving CE are embedded in a wider institutional environment where formal rules (laws, regulations, constitutions) interact with informal ones (social norms, traditions, values) [1]. This institutional environment profoundly shapes the behaviours of businesses, consumers, and public authorities. While laws have traditionally targeted the points of highest environmental impact—such as waste disposal, manufacturing emissions, or raw material extraction—they often neglect the use phase of products or the systemic interactions between stages of a product's life. For CE to be effective, legal frameworks must evolve to cover the entire lifecycle of goods and services. In this context, laws and regulations act as enabling infrastructures, creating the institutional conditions for circular business models and consumer behaviours to emerge and thrive.

2.2 THE ROLE OF REGULATION IN THE LINEAR-TO-CIRCULAR TRANSITION

The shift from a linear to a circular economy is not purely a technical or business innovation challenge—it is deeply political and institutional. Regulation, as a set of binding rules and formalized governance structures, is one of the most powerful tools for enabling or hindering this transformation. Regulation provides directionality by shaping market conditions, reducing uncertainty, and aligning incentives. It plays a strategic role in addressing systemic barriers, such as lock-ins in linear production-consumption patterns and is essential for coordinating the multiplicity of actors involved in CE implementation. Public policies—understood broadly as a combination of laws, regulatory measures, strategic documents (such as roadmaps and action plans), and funding priorities—are enacted at multiple levels of governance, from international to local. These policies employ a variety of instruments, typically categorized into administrative (e.g. bans, standards), economic (e.g. subsidies, taxes), and informative (e.g. eco-labels, public campaigns) tools. Most policy instruments are operationalized through laws, but laws also

provide the legal boundaries within which policy instruments can be applied. For example, EU procurement law does not prescribe the sustainability criteria public buyers must use, but it sets principles—such as non-discrimination—that shape how national and local policies can be designed.

Despite advancements, many laws have historically focused on end-of-pipe solutions—regulating environmental impacts at the point of waste disposal or emission—rather than addressing the full lifecycle of products. A shift is needed towards laws that address design, production, consumption, and reuse stages. As noted in the literature, due to the global nature of supply chains and trade in resources, national-level regulations are insufficient. A harmonized international and supranational regulatory approach is necessary to prevent regulatory fragmentation, ensure fairness, and reduce implementation costs for economic actors operating across borders [2].

Empirical evidence indicates that the real-world implementation of circular economy policies remains fragmented and often superficial. Firm-level uptake of circular practices appears limited [3], and a significant gap persists between regulatory intent and actual business practice [4]. There is little evidence of a direct causal link between regulation and changes in individual or organisational behaviour. Instead, circular practices tend to be shaped by a broader set of factors, including economic incentives such as tax rebates or penalties, environmental conditions like resource scarcity, demographic variables such as household size, consumer psychology related to risk perception and environmental concern, and product characteristics such as ease of use, design quality, and brand image [5]. While policy instruments may not directly trigger behavioural change, they are often regarded as necessary conditions for circular economy adoption, as they help create the context and incentives that support the transition, even if they are not sufficient on their own to shift mindsets.

Moreover, the effectiveness of EU CE policy varies significantly across Member States, raising questions about its inclusiveness and uniformity. Differences in public awareness, cultural attitudes, administrative capacity, and economic structure affect how CE policies are received and implemented. Only some regulatory instruments are binding, and their enforcement remains uneven. In many cases, the societal support needed to make policies effective is lacking, resulting in limited behavioural change. Understanding the reasons behind the resistance or low engagement of individuals and organizations is critical. Are these barriers financial, cultural, or institutional? Which regulatory instruments are perceived as supportive, and which are seen as obstructive? These questions point to a broader research agenda that could inform future policy design.

2.3 THE INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN REGULATORY CONTEXT

In the international context, China stands out as a pioneer, having launched a CE strategy as early as 2003 to address environmental degradation caused by rapid industrialization. This culminated in the 2009 Circular Economy Promotion Law, the first national legislation specifically targeting CE principles. Meanwhile, since the early 2000s, CE policies have been adopted in multiple countries, though their scope and ambition vary widely. Given the global nature of supply chains and trade in materials, isolated national actions are insufficient. Coordination of policies and international cooperation is crucial to avoid regulatory fragmentation, facilitate fair competition, and ensure broad implementation of CE principles. The Global Alliance on Circular Economy and Resource Efficiency (GACERE), launched in 2021 by the EU, UNEP, UNIDO, and other partners (including the Ellen MacArthur Foundation), represents one such effort to foster international collaboration.

Within the European Union, the CE has progressively become a cornerstone of environmental and industrial strategy. Early efforts included the Europe 2020 Strategy and the 2011 Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe. In 2014, the European Commission launched the communication “Towards a circular economy: a zero-waste programme for Europe”, highlighting the economic rationale for CE. However, it was the 2015 action plan “Closing the Loop” that marked a turning point. This plan adopted a lifecycle approach and integrated circularity into existing legal frameworks. It covered production and consumption, waste management, and the market for secondary raw materials. Among its key measures were the revision of EU waste legislation, the launch of the Eco-design Working Plan 2016–2019, the development of product and organization environmental footprint methodologies, and harmonized rules for organic fertilizers derived from secondary raw materials.

The transition to the circular economy certainly rests on the package “Circular Economy”, consisting of the four Directives adopted by the European Parliament and the Council on 30 May 2018. These are Directives 851/2018/EU, “Waste Directive”, 852/2018/EU, “Packaging Directive”, 850/2018/EU, “Landfill Directive” and 849/2018/EU, “Vehicles, Batteries, WEEE Directive”. The Circular Economy Package identifies five priority sectors to accelerate the transition along their value chain: plastics, food waste, essential raw materials, construction and demolition, biomass and biological materials.

By 2019, the European Commission had delivered 54 actions under this plan and declared its implementation complete. However, new challenges, including the rise of digital technologies, increasing public concern for sustainability, and the urgency of climate change, called for a more ambitious agenda. In this light, the European Green Deal, launched in 2019, framed the CE as a fundamental component of the EU's climate neutrality objective. The new Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP II), adopted in 2020, focuses on resource-intensive sectors and key value

chains, including electronics, ICT, batteries and vehicles, packaging, plastics, textiles, construction, and food. It combines legislative and non-legislative initiatives aimed at improving product durability, reparability, reusability, and recyclability. Notable examples include the 2022 proposal for a Regulation on Eco-design for Sustainable Products, the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles, and a revised Construction Products Regulation. The strategy includes the development of a digital product passport, rules to tackle greenwashing, harmonized extended producer responsibility (EPR) for textiles, and economic incentives to discourage overproduction and overconsumption. In parallel, the EU also revised its Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive and issued communications on biodegradable and compostable plastics. Legislative proposals to substantiate green claims and reduce microplastic pollution were also announced. Recent literature [6] highlights the need to move beyond the narrow vision of the consumer as a passive end-user. Individuals can take on multiple roles as producers, users, sharers, repairers, and innovators. Effective regulation must therefore consider the diverse ways people and organizations engage with circularity. As such, the role of regulation is not only to direct behaviour but also to empower action. Future CE policy must evolve to be more inclusive, adaptive, and grounded in empirical evidence, ensuring that it facilitates real transformations rather than merely symbolic ones.

3. MAPPING OF EXISTING POLICIES AND REGULATIONS

The regulatory framework is a crucial driver in the transition to a circular economy, providing clear guidelines, incentives, and obligations that shape business strategies and market dynamics. Chapter 3 maps the existing policies and regulations that underpin this transition, examining how they operate at European, national, and regional levels, and how they shape practices in key sectors such as waste management, construction, and textiles.

The chapter begins with an analysis of European-level waste management strategies, focusing on the legal regimes of by-products and End-of-Waste (EoW), as well as the integration of Minimum Environmental Criteria (CAM) into Green Public Procurement (GPP). These instruments illustrate how EU directives and national transpositions, such as Italy's Environmental Code and its subsequent ministerial decrees, have established a regulatory foundation for resource recovery, eco-design, and the reduction of environmental impacts.

It then explores planning instruments at the regional level, with a focus on Piedmont and Lombardy, which provide practical examples of how EU directives are translated into local waste management strategies and prevention programs. The analysis highlights the role of regional plans in promoting reuse, recycling, and energy recovery while discouraging landfilling.

Finally, the chapter examines two sector-specific case studies — construction and demolition waste and the textile sector — where recent regulatory developments, such as Italy's 2024 decree on construction End-of-Waste criteria and the forthcoming EU-wide Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) for textiles, represent crucial steps towards achieving the EU's 2035 circularity targets. These cases illustrate how regulatory innovations can not only reduce waste and resource consumption but also create incentives for eco-design, reuse, and transparency along the value chain.

3.1 WASTE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES: POLICIES AND REGULATIONS AT THE EUROPEAN LEVEL

As a general principle, waste management strategies, both at the European and national levels, are based on the recovery and valorisation of the waste generated, thereby contributing to a reduction in the consumption of natural resources and raw materials [7].

The waste rules apply essentially whenever a substance qualifies as waste under art. 183 (1), point (a), and until it ceases to be such under art. 184-ter of the Legislative Decree 3 April 2006, n. 152 (hereinafter “Environmental Code”), thus being able to be freely marketed as a product: in this last case, we also talk about EoW.

There are, however, cases where a substance does not acquire the status of waste, even though it constitutes a “residue” of a production process: under certain conditions, it qualifies as a “by-product” within the meaning of Article 184-bis of the Environmental Code.

Both legal regimes (EoW and by-product) therefore have an impact on the application of the rules on waste and, consequently, on the compliance obligations incumbent upon operators in the course of their activities.

3.1.1 By-products

Where certain conditions are met, a substance or object resulting from a production process, that the primary purpose of which is not the production of that substance or object, shall not be regarded as waste; as such, it may be placed on the market without being subject to the requirements applicable to waste.

The concept of a by-product has consistently raised questions as regards the conditions set out in Article 184-bis p.1. of the Environmental Code. To dispel, at least in part, such doubts, Ministerial Decree of 13 October 2016, No. 264 (hereinafter “MD 264/16”) and the related Ministerial Interpretative Circular of 30 May 2017, protocol No. 7619 (“Circular No. 7619/2017”) were adopted.

Pursuant to Article 1, point (c) of MD 264/16, a by-product is defined as *“a production residue which does not constitute waste within the meaning of Article 184-bis of Legislative Decree of 3 April 2006, No. 152”*, further specifying, in the first paragraph of the following Article 4, that *“materials are to be regarded as products and not as waste where the producer demonstrates that, not having been intentionally produced as the primary objective of the production cycle, they are intended for use in the same or in a subsequent process, either by the producer himself or by third parties.”* By-products are therefore residues which the producer does not intend to discard, and which are generated by a production process of which they are not the principal product. The legislator further subjects the classification as a by-product to the cumulative fulfilment, by the producer, of the conditions laid down in Article 184-bis of the Environmental Code.

One of the most critical aspects relating to the qualification of by-products concerns the notion of “normal industrial practice”: in this regard, Article 6 of MD 264/16 provides a dual definition, both negative and positive. Paragraph 1 stipulates that *“processes and operations necessary to ensure that the environmental characteristics of the substance or object meet, for the specific use, all relevant requirements concerning products, the protection of health and the environment, and that do not lead to overall negative environmental impacts, shall not constitute normal industrial practice, unless they are carried out within the same production cycle, in accordance with paragraph 2”*; paragraph 2 further provides that *“activities and operations that form an integral part of the production cycle of the residue shall, in any case, fall within normal industrial practice, even if designed and implemented for the specific purpose of ensuring that the environmental or health characteristics of the substance or object meet all*

relevant requirements concerning products, the protection of health and the environment, and do not lead to overall negative environmental impacts.”

Circular No. 7619/2017, in turn, illustrates the two prevailing approaches in case-law: for the purpose of demonstrating that the operation falls within 'normal industrial practice', the operator may prove, by way of example, that:

- the treatment does not affect or cause the material to lose its identity, commercial characteristics or environmental quality, does not cause a structural alteration of the chemical-physical components of the substance or in its radical transformation (Cass. pen. n. 40109/2015 and Cass. pen. n. 17453/2012).
- the treatment corresponds to the operations ordinarily carried out in the production process in which the material is used, and in particular to those ordinarily performed on the raw material which the by-product replaces (Cass. pen. n. 17453/2012; Cass. pen. n. 20886/2013).

In any case, case-law remains closely linked to the examination of the specific circumstances of each individual case.

A useful reference tool is the website [ESP](#) (*Elenco dei Produttori e degli Utilizzatori di Sottoprodotti*); in this regard, it should be noted that the register does not constitute an enabling requirement for producers or users of by-products, but serves solely for information purposes and to facilitate exchanges. The qualification of a material as a by-product, and therefore not as waste, is independent of the producer's or user's registration in the abovementioned list. This qualification is of an objective nature and is determined by demonstrating compliance with the requirements laid down in Article 184-bis of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006. Accordingly, inclusion in the register by the producer or user, in itself, is not sufficient to qualify a residue as a by-product; conversely, failure to register does not automatically result in the classification of the residue as waste.

3.1.2 End of Waste (EoW)

Article 184-ter of the Environmental Code also provides for the End of Waste (EoW), in implementation of Directive 2008/98/EC, namely the “cessation of waste status” which substantially corresponds to what, under the previous Article 181-bis of the same Code, was referred to as the production of “secondary raw materials.” A waste ceases to be waste because, through a dedicated industrial process, it is reprocessed into a product that is freely marketable and usable. The resulting product has a market value and can be managed without the restrictions and formalities applicable to waste.

In order to prevent speculative fraud, this operation must be strictly regulated, and the conditions under which it may take place must be precisely defined. As regards detailed rules, in the absence of EU provisions, the Directive leaves Member States free, in principle, to provide either through general measures (ministerial decrees) or even on a “case-by-case” basis.

Following Directive (EU) 2018/851 of 30 May 2018, which, in the framework of measures aimed at promoting the so-called circular economy [8], amended Article 6 of Directive 2008/98, the Italian legislator, through Decree-Law of 3 September 2019 No. 101, converted into Law of 2 November 2019 No. 128, amended national provisions by expressly introducing the possibility of determining, on a “case-by-case” basis (and not only by means of general ministerial decrees), the criteria under which the material processed in a specific facility loses its waste status, in order to foster the development of pilot facilities based on innovative technologies.

Therefore, the specific criteria for recognising EoW may be established either by EU legislation or, in its absence, by the Member States, through general measures (ministerial decrees) or on a “case-by-case” basis, in the framework of issuing the Integrated Environmental Authorisation or the authorisations referred to in Articles 208, 209 and 211 of the Environmental Code [9].

During the preliminary phase, the competent authorities must refer, in addition to the conditions laid down in Article 184-ter (1), the “detailed criteria” referred to in Article 184-ter (3) of Legislative Decree 152/2006.

At Union level, End-of-Waste (EoW) criteria have been established by means of specific Regulations for the following materials: iron, steel and aluminium – Regulation (EU) No. 333/2011; glass cullet – Regulation (EU) No. 1179/2012; copper and copper alloys – Regulation (EU) No. 715/2013.

At national level, six Ministerial Decrees have been adopted regulating EoW criteria for specific waste streams: Ministerial Decree of 14 February 2013, No. 22 (solid recovered fuel); Ministerial Decree of 28 March 2018, No. 69 (bituminous conglomerate); Ministerial Decree of 15 May 2019, No. 62 (absorbent hygiene products); Ministerial Decree of 31 March 2020, No. 78 (recycled rubber from end-of-life tyres); Ministerial Decree of 22 September 2020, No. 188 (paper and cardboard); Ministerial Decree of 27 September 2022, No. 152 (construction and demolition waste), repealed and replaced by Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024.

As regards “case-by-case” authorisations, since 30 September 2021 the RECER system is operational: this is the National Register for the collection of authorisations granted and the outcomes of simplified procedures concluded for the purpose of carrying out waste recovery operations. RECER is divided into two sections: one dedicated to ordinary authorisations, i.e. measures adopted pursuant to Articles 208, 209 and 211 and Title III-bis of Part Two of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006 (Integrated Environmental Authorisation – AIA); the other dedicated to the outcomes of simplified procedures, pursuant to Articles 214 and 216 of the same Decree. This national database is intended to ensure compliance with the principles of transparency and public accessibility of authorisations, and to provide as complete a picture as possible of the facilities carrying out waste recovery, thereby facilitating monitoring and control activities.

3.1.3 Minimum environmental criteria (CAM)

Public authorities also play a key role in promoting circular economy models through Green Public Procurement (GPP), that is, environmentally friendly purchasing, which stimulates the market for recyclable products and services with a low environmental impact through the leverage of public demand.

Since the adoption of the Green Paper “Public Procurement in the European Union” in 1996, the European Commission has shown increasing attention to environmental protection policies in public procurement, considering that “environmental protection can be achieved through technical specifications concerning the characteristics of the works, supplies or services which are the subject of procurement, that is to say, the technical specifications which contracting authorities must set out in the general procurement documents and which tenderers must comply with, as required by the directives” (paragraph 5.49).

These policies are embedded in the instrument of Green Public Procurement (GPP), defined as “the approach whereby public authorities integrate environmental criteria into all stages of the procurement process, encouraging the dissemination of environmental technologies and the development of environmentally sound products, through the search for and selection of results and solutions that have the least possible impact on the environment throughout their entire life cycle.” The objective of GPP is to incorporate environmental considerations into the purchasing processes of public authorities and to guide their choices towards goods, services and works that have the lowest environmental impact, thereby fostering the development of a market and a culture that are more environmentally aware.

The integration of environmental aspects into procurement processes is based on the consideration of the entire life cycle: goods, services and works must be assessed taking into account their full life cycle, from the composition of materials to the modalities of use, disposal or recycling.

Subsequently, the Commission adopted the Communication to the Council and the European Parliament COM(2003) of 18 June 2003, emphasising the need to integrate environmental requirements into public procurement through dedicated action plans, with the aim of “giving political impetus to the process of implementing the measures necessary to promote greater consideration of environmental aspects in public procurement and awareness-raising initiatives, allowing Member States to choose the solutions that best fit their policy framework and the level already achieved, while at the same time enabling the exchange of best practices in the field” (paragraph 5.3, box 3, point (a)).

On the basis of that Communication, and in implementation of the provisions of the 2007 Finance Act (Article 1, paragraphs 1126–1128 of Law No. 296/2006), by Decree of the Minister for the Environment and the Protection of Land and Sea of 11 April 2008 No. 135, in agreement with the Ministry of Economy and Finance and the Ministry of Economic Development, the “Action Plan for the Environmental Sustainability of Consumption in the Public Administration Sector” was

approved, with the aim of promoting the dissemination of GPP among public authorities as a tool for environmental improvement.

In particular, the Italian Action Plan aims not only to spread awareness of GPP within the public sector, but also, more specifically, to define, for goods, services and works identified as priorities due to their environmental impact and expenditure volumes, methodological guidelines for the development of “sustainable” procurement processes and environmental criteria to be incorporated into tender specifications.

For this purpose, minimum environmental criteria have been adopted for public procurement tenders, covering a wide range of sectors (“energy services for buildings – lighting and motive power services – heating/cooling services”, “design services and works for the construction, renovation and maintenance of public buildings”, “public green area management services and supply of products for green area maintenance,” etc.).

The rationale for the mandatory nature of minimum environmental criteria lies in the need to ensure that national policy on green public procurement is effective not only in reducing environmental impacts but also in promoting more sustainable, circular production and consumption models and in fostering green jobs (Cons. Stato n. 6934/2022). As a result, contracting authorities, while exercising the discretion conferred by the Public Procurement Code, may not attribute to CAM an excessively low, or negligible, weight, under penalty of frustrating the purpose of the primary legislation, which aims to ensure that the environmental aspect is relevant in the selection procedure (and not only during the performance phase of the contract) and also in the qualitative assessment of technical tenders (TAR Roma n. 19910/2024). Consequently, the public procurement contract, from being a mere instrument for the acquisition of goods and services, becomes a tool of economic policy, serving the implementation of public policies that go beyond the immediate contractual object: in particular, so-called green public procurement is characterised as a “segment of the circular economy” (Cons. Stato n. 8773/2022).

3.1.4 Extended Producer responsibility (EPR)

Another key instrument aimed at promoting the transition towards a circular economy at European level is Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR): anyone placing a product or service on the market must ensure the proper management of its entire life cycle, including the post-consumption phase [\[10\]](#).

An accurate definition of the principle of EPR is provided by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), according to which the Extended Producer Responsibility is “an environmental policy approach in which a producer’s responsibility for a product is extended to the post-consumer stage of a product’s life cycle” (OECD, “Extended Producer Responsibility: A Guidance Manual for Governments”, Paris, March 2001, p. 164). In particular, according to the OECD, the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) is a policy

approach under which producers are given a significant responsibility – financial and/or physical – for the treatment or disposal of post-consumer products. Assigning such responsibility could in principle provide incentives to prevent wastes at the source, promote product design for the environment and support the achievement of public recycling and materials management goals” (cf. [OECD](#)).

According to this principle, therefore, producer responsibility is extended to the post-consumer stage of a product's life cycle. The main benefits of implementing EPR schemes are the ability to reduce the burden on government and citizens, to increase material recycling and internalise environmental costs in production and consumption processes, to promote eco-design and re-use of products, to provide incentives for those who market more durable products that put less pressure on the environment.

The EPR schemes are based on the consideration that end-of-life management is a cost item for the producer; as a result, producers of a non-recyclable product will spend more on post-consumption, compared with the producer of the same product, but recyclable.

The implementation of EPR schemes has resulted in the use of upstream eco-design, that is to say at the product production stage, where eco-design must be based on a careful study of the life cycle of the product, LCA, in the sense that each of the five phases composing LCA, extraction of resources and processing, production, packaging and transport, use and disposal must be carried out in accordance with the principles of environmental sustainability.

The final result of EPR is the transfer of the end-of-life cost of a product from the community to the producer of the product [\[1\]](#).

At the European level, with regard to the EPR instrument, reference should be made to Directive 2008/98/EC. In particular, art. 8 of Directive 2008/98/EC introduced in general terms extended producer responsibility, providing that it may be applied, by the provision by Member States of legislative or non-legislative measures, to any individual person or legal person who professionally develops, manufactures, processes, trades, sells or amounts produced (producer of the product) and specifying the objectives of EPR, namely the strengthening of reuse, prevention, recycling and other waste recovery [\[12\]](#).

Such measures may include the acceptance of returned products and waste remaining after use of those products, as well as subsequent waste management and financial responsibility for those activities. Such measures may include an obligation to make publicly available information on the extent to which the product is reusable and recyclable.

Moreover, still according to art. 8, paragraph 2, Directive 2008/98/EC, Member States may take appropriate measures to encourage product design aimed at reducing their environmental impacts and the generation of waste during production and subsequent use of products and to ensure that the recovery and disposal of products that have become waste are carried out in accordance with the rules of the same Directive (articles 4 and 13).

The rule also provides that these measures may encourage the development, production and marketing of products suitable for multiple uses, technically durable and which, after becoming waste, are suitable for appropriate and safe recovery and environmentally friendly disposal [\[13\]](#).

Finally, when applying Extended Producer responsibility, Member States should take into account technical feasibility and economic practicability as well as the overall social, health and environmental impacts, respecting the need to ensure the proper functioning of the internal market.

Directive 2008/98/EC has been amended by Directive 2018/851/EU. Considering XXI of the Directive states that Extended producer responsibility schemes are essential elements for good waste management.

However, the efficiency and effectiveness of these schemes vary considerably from one Member State to another. It is therefore necessary to define minimum performance requirements and to make clear that those requirements also apply to extended producer responsibility schemes established under other Union legislation.

According to the above-mentioned provision, while it remains the discretion of the Member States to adopt or not, through legislative and non-legislative measures, EPR schemes, given that Art. 8 (1), para. 1 of Directive 2008/98 has not been amended by the 2018 reform, where such measures include the establishment of extended producer responsibility schemes, the general minimum requirements set out in Article 8-bis shall apply (Art. 8 (1), para. 3, as amended by art. 1, point 8), letter a), Directive 851/2018).

In other words, the Directive 851/2018 did not introduce an obligation to implementation EPR schemes, but provided that, where the national legislator has decided to implementation EPR schemes, the general minimum requirements introduced by art. 8-bis which defined a uniform statute valid for all extended producer responsibility schemes must be applied.

According to art. 8-bis, the general minimum requirements include: a) defining the roles and responsibilities of all relevant actors involved, including producers; b) setting waste management targets to achieve the quantitative targets relevant for the extended producer responsibility regime; c) ensuring that an information reporting system is in place to collect data on products placed on the market of the Member State; d) ensuring fair treatment of producers, irrespective of their origin or size.

In the national legal system, the principle of EPR was provided by art. 178-bis, Legislative Decree No. 152/2006, introduced by Legislative Decree No. 205/2010.

According to art. 178 bis (3), Legislative Decree No. 152/2006, the extended producer responsibility schemes established by the decrees provided for paragraph 1 shall provide for appropriate measures to encourage a design of products and their components aimed at reducing their environmental impacts and waste generation during production and subsequent use of products and to ensure that the recovery and disposal of products which have become waste

takes place in accordance with the priority criteria laid down in art. 179 and in compliance with paragraph 4 of art. 177.

Such measures shall encourage, inter alia, the development, production and marketing of products and product components suitable for multiple use, containing recycled materials that are technically durable and easily repairable and which, after becoming waste, are suitable for preparation for re-use and recycling to support the correct implementation of the waste hierarchy. The measures shall take into account the impact of the entire product life cycle, the waste hierarchy and, where appropriate, the potential for multiple recycling.

With Legislative Decree No. 116/2020 was given implementation to the regulation contained in Directive 2018/851/EU, through the modification of art. 178-bis and the introduction of art. 178-ter, relating to the general minimum requirements that EPR schemes must comply with.

With the transposition of Directive 2018/851/EC, the pre-existing provision contained in art. 178-bis, which provided for the possibility of adopting EPR schemes, has been superseded by the current provision that establishes that are extended producer responsibility schemes, making their adoption compulsory.

3.2 POLICIES AND PLANNING INSTRUMENTS AT THE LOCAL LEVEL (PIEDMONT AND LOMBARDY)

The regulatory framework that forms the backdrop to the update of the Regional Urban Waste Management Plan of the Piedmont region, approved with Resolution of the Regional Council n. 277-11379 of 9 May 2023 and the update of the Regional Urban Waste Management Program of the Lombardy region, approved with Resolution of the Regional Council n. 6408 of 23 May 2022 is represented, in particular, by the package “Circular Economy”, consisting of the four Directives adopted by the European Parliament and the Council on 30 May 2018. These are Directives 851/2018/EU, “Waste Directive”, 852/2018/EU, “Packaging Directive”, 850/2018/EU, “Landfill Directive” and 849/2018/EU, “Vehicles, Batteries, WEEE Directive”. The package “Circular Economy” set new binding targets for waste reduction, to be achieved at EU level by 2025, 2030 and 2035. Specifically, these are: new recycling targets for municipal waste (55% by 2025, 60% by 2030, 65% by 2035); new targets for recycling packaging waste (65% by 2025, 70% by 2030); a binding target to reduce landfilling for all waste to a maximum of 10% by 2035. The package “Circular Economy” established on the one hand a ban on landfill disposal of waste from separate collection and on the other hand the promotion of economic instruments to discourage landfilling; it also provided measures and objectives to reduce food waste (by 30% by 2025, by 50% by 2030), economic incentives for the production of greener products to be placed on the market and support measures for recovery and recycling systems (e.g. for packaging, batteries, electrical and electronic equipment, vehicles).

The Directives of the circular economy package were implemented through four legislative decrees adopted on 7 August 2020: Legislative Decree 116/2020, so-called “Waste Decree” which jointly transposes Directives 851/2018 and 852/2018, Legislative Decree 121/2020 which transposes Directive 850/2018 on landfills, Legislative Decree 118/2020 and Legislative Decree 119/2020 which transpose Directive 849/2018 on WEEE, waste from batteries and accumulators and on end-of-life vehicles.

In accordance with art. 198 bis (2) of Legislative Decree 152/2006, with the PNGR, National Waste Management Plan, to be adopted by the Minister of the Environment, the criteria and strategic guidelines to be followed by the regions and autonomous provinces in drawing up the Waste Management Plans must be defined.

Both plans represent the programming tool through which the Piedmont Region and the Lombardy Region define in an integrated manner the policies regarding the prevention, recycling, recovery and landfill disposal of waste, as well as the management of polluted sites to be reclaimed.

In the first section of the Regional Urban Waste Management Plan of the Piedmont [14] the results of the analysis of the production of municipal waste and special waste in Piedmont are given, taking 2019 as the reference year.

From the analysis carried out, it emerged that in 2019, approximately 58.0% of the undifferentiated urban waste corresponding to 787,419 tonnes was sent for energy recovery at the waste-to-energy plant located in the municipality of Turin, 41.4% in plants of TMB (Mechanical Biological Treatment) located in the Region and, finally, 0.6% in landfill.

A certainly positive data is represented by the significant reduction in the quantity of undifferentiated urban waste sent to landfill (from approximately 639,000 tonnes in 2010 to 4,500 tonnes in 2019), a reduction which corresponded to an increase in the use of waste-to-energy, while the use of mechanical treatment biological has remained practically constant in a range between 320,000 t and 354,000 t.

The Regional Urban Waste Management Plan identifies the general objectives that it intends to pursue: preventing the production of waste; increase preparation for reuse and recycling, i.e. the recovery of material; promote energy recovery for waste fractions for which the recovery of material is not technically and economically possible, in order to reduce its disposal in landfill (direct or indirect disposal, following treatment); minimize the use of landfill disposal; encourage the creation of a territorial plant system that allows compliance with the principle of proximity, guaranteeing the environmental and economic sustainability of the waste cycle [15]. The main actions that the Piedmont Region intends to undertake to achieve the objectives mentioned are indicated below.

With regard to the prevention of waste production, the Piedmont Region intends to promote, also through the provision of economic incentives, eco-design and eco-design. With reference to the need to prevent food waste, the aim is to adopt actions to devolve food surpluses (such as, for

example: collection of food in commercial activities and food and meals not distributed in collective catering with the aim of allocating them to support people living in conditions of food poverty).

The second objective, i.e. the recovery of material, can be achieved by pursuing, as specific objectives, throughout the regional territory, the separate collection of at least the following fractions: organic, green, paper, metals, plastic, glass, wood, textiles, WEEE, bulky, including mattresses and furniture and providing, at the same time, for the consolidation of home collection services and the reorganization and/or optimization of collection services.

The third objective of the Plan focuses on promoting the use of energy recovery, only where the recovery of material is not possible. In compliance with the hierarchy of priorities in waste management, energy recovery can only be taken into consideration where the recovery of material is not possible, technically and economically. The following are identified as specific objectives to be pursued under the third objective: the increase in the production and use of energy from waste-to-energy; the valorisation of the various components constituting biogas from waste (e.g. CH₄, CO₂), the guarantee of an efficient level of collection of biogas from landfill and its recovery.

Through the fourth objective, the aim is to minimize the use of landfill, in line with the hierarchy of priorities regarding waste management. The reduction of the quantities of waste sent to landfill, both in the Region and in neighbouring regions, as a specific objective, will be achieved through: actions to promote treatments aimed at avoiding the landfill disposal of waste from the treatment of urban waste, both deriving from separate waste collection, and deriving from undifferentiated urban waste; activities aimed at maximizing the recovery of bulky waste and street sweeping waste; identification of fiscal instruments in order to discourage landfill disposal. The fifth and final objective identified in the Plan takes on a general value and translates into the need to encourage the creation of a territorial plant system that allows compliance with the principle of proximity, guaranteeing the environmental and economic sustainability of the waste cycle, reducing the transport of extra-region waste. The result to be achieved through the implementation of the fifth objective is represented by the zeroing of the delivery to other regions of undifferentiated municipal waste as well as the waste resulting from their treatment in Mechanical Biological Treatment plants and the zeroing of the unmet requirement for treatment of the biodegradable organic fraction from separate collection calculated on the new collection objectives.

The first section of the Regional Urban Waste Management Program [16] of the Lombardy region contains the analysis of the production of municipal waste and special waste in Lombardy, referring to the data relating to the 2018-2019 years, as these are the most recent data available at the time of drafting the Program.

The Program specifies that in Lombardy the overall production of urban waste in 2019 was 4,840,740 t, equal to 479.1 kg/abx and that in 2019 separate waste collection reached the regional average of 72% with peaks of virtuous municipal realities which stand permanently above '80%. The percentage of separate waste collection at municipal level has grown steadily over the last ten years. It therefore emerges that in Lombardy in recent years a significant efficiency of collection services has made it possible to achieve important goals such as the decrease and stabilization of per capita waste production and the simultaneous increase in the percentage of separate waste collection.

The collection model that led to these results is the door-to-door one (extended to over '80% of Lombardy municipalities) which, in some contexts, has equipped itself with a monitoring system necessary and preliminary to the possible implementation of the punctual tariff based on the key concept "polluter pays" (declined to PAYT - Pay As You Throw).

As regards special waste, in 2018 (latest data available) almost 33 million tonnes of waste were produced, of which 92% is made up of non-hazardous waste and the remaining 8% is made up of hazardous waste. Overall, special waste represents approximately 87% of the total production of Lombardy waste.

The Program then sets a series of objectives, starting with the forecast of achieving 65% separate waste collection in all Lombardy municipalities in 2027.

Another objective that Lombardy sets itself, in line with the European hierarchy, is "zero landfill": this disposal method must only be used in residual form for those fractions that cannot be recovered in terms of matter and energy.

The 2022-2027 Prevention Programme, a specific plan and an integral part of the Program, focuses its action on 5 areas of intervention that the Lombardy Region considers strategic with a view to achieving the objectives of the circular economy: 1) prevention of food waste (Legislative Decree 116/2020 provides for the adoption of a specific prevention plan for food waste) through promotion of the short supply chain also through support for the development of "Solidarity purchasing groups", guidelines for collective catering, environmental education in schools, support for food devolution; 2) promotion of reuse, through financing calls for implementation and management optimization; (3) prevention of single-use products; (4) prevention of microplastics; (5) spread of punctual tariff, that is, parameterized to the quantity of undifferentiated waste produced, with the aim of reaching 20% of Lombardy municipalities at punctual tariff by 2027.

With regard to the waste treatment plants present in the area, the requirement for new waste treatment plants dedicated to incineration in Lombardy for non-hazardous urban and special waste does not emerge. The Program establishes new localization criteria in order to encourage the "zero km" treatment of waste. It provides for the installation of new waste recovery facilities, in the perspective of the circular economy, in the perimeter or in areas adjacent to existing

production or waste treatment facilities, dedicated exclusively to the final recovery of waste deriving from such facilities.

The Program envisages the adoption of Regional Programmes for the prevention of food waste with actions extended to the entire food production chain, from “reduction of food waste in primary production, in processing and manufacturing, up to the final stage of consumption. Among the planned actions we can mention, by way of example, the development of “Solidarity purchasing groups” in public and private entities with a certain number of employees, the promotion of products outside the aesthetic license fee and the publication of regional calls for the establishment of neighbourhood hubs for devolution of food surpluses.

3.3 AN EVOLVING REGULATION: EoW AND TEXTILE EPR

Two strategic sectors that may play a crucial role in achieving the European Union’s circular economy objectives by 2035 are those of construction and demolition waste and textile waste.

A. As regards construction and demolition waste and other mineral-based inert waste, the rules governing the End-of-Waste (EoW) status are laid down in Ministerial Decree No. 127 of 28 June 2024 [17], issued by the Ministry for the Environment and Energy Security, which replaces Ministerial Decree No. 152 of 27 September 2022 [18][19]. The revision of this Regulation was one of the key items in the recent regulatory activity of the Ministry, in view of the environmental and economic benefits associated with increased recovery of inert waste and the resulting reduction in landfill disposal.

This decree, the result of a long preparatory process aimed at promoting the recovery of a major waste stream in order to support the circular economy and reduce the consumption of natural resources, lays down the criteria under which recycled aggregates used in civil engineering works may be used as substitutes for natural raw materials. These are materials with real economic value, which — when used for specific purposes and in compliance with the criteria set out in the ministerial regulation — do not cause overall adverse impacts on human health or the environment.

The procedure leading to the adoption of this decree is lengthy and structured. It includes a preliminary consultation with ISPRA (the Italian National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research) and ISSalute (Italian National Institute of Health), which verify that the use of the substance or object does not result in overall negative effects on human health or the environment. This is followed by a public consultation phase to collect feedback from civil society and stakeholders. The draft decree is then revised by the competent departments of the Ministry and submitted to the Council of State for its opinion. After its final adoption, the draft is subject to a three-month standstill period before the European Commission, to ensure that the technical regulation does not create barriers to the internal market.

The regulation sets out the specific criteria under which inert waste from construction and demolition activities and other mineral-based inert waste cease to be classified as waste following recovery operations pursuant to Article 184-ter of the Environmental Code. This condition is met only if the material subject to recovery operations complies with the criteria laid down in Annex 1 and is used exclusively for the specific purposes listed in Annex 2.

Compliance with these criteria is certified by the producers of recovered aggregates through a self-declaration of conformity and statutory declaration, which must be submitted to the competent authority and to the regionally competent Environmental Protection Agency within six months of the date of production of the batch of recovered aggregate, and in any case before it leaves the plant.

Recovery operations intended to achieve End-of-Waste status that involve waste not listed in Table 1 of Annex 1, or waste intended for purposes other than those listed in Annex 2, are subject to the granting or renewal of an authorisation pursuant to Article 184-ter. However, the “case-by-case” authorisation remains an exception and may not be used to exclude from the scope of the regulation any waste included in Table 1 of Annex 1.

B. On the textile sector, the data published by the Council of the European Union show that the EU generates 12.6 million tonnes of textile waste a year. Clothing and footwear alone account for 5.2 million tonnes of waste, equivalent to 12 kg of waste per person each year (cf. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/it>).

The textile sector is one of the industrial sectors with the greatest environmental impact due to especially an inefficient management of textile waste and the spread of cd. “Fast Fashion”. In this situation, the introduction of an extended producer responsibility system - Extended Producer Responsibility or “EPR” - represents a fundamental tool towards the realization of a more sustainable and circular textile economy.

At European level, in February 2025 the presidency of the Council of the European Union and the European Parliament reached an Interim Agreement on a revision of the Waste Framework Directive, Directive 2008/98/EC. The final adoption of the revised Directive by the European Parliament is expected in autumn 2025. The Interim Agreement sets targets for reducing food waste by 2030 and textile waste reduction targets and measures to transform the textile sector into a more sustainable and circular one.

With regard to textile waste, the Interim Agreement establishes harmonised rules on Extended Producer Responsibility for textiles and fashion brands; textiles and fashion brands will be responsible for their waste and will be required to pay a fee to help finance the collection and treatment of waste; the eco-design of the product shall be taken into account in determining the amount of the tariff according to circularity and sustainability criteria (e.g. durability of textile products and durability of products).

The implementation of harmonised Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes is in addition to the obligation laid down from January 2025 (and already respected by Italy since 2022) to collect textile waste separately.

According to the Interim Agreement, Member States will have 20 months from the entry into force of the Directive to transpose it into their national law and 30 months to activate EPR systems. Under EPR schemes, producers who make textile products available on the EU market will have to cover the costs of their proper collection, sorting, preparation for reuse and recycling. Companies will have to comply with EPR requirements 12 months after the activation of EPR systems by their respective Member States. The provisions of the Directive will apply to all producers, including those using e-commerce tools and regardless of whether they are established in an EU country or outside the EU.

The Interim Agreement gives the European Commission the task of reviewing and evaluating various aspects of the Waste Framework Directive relating to textiles, including the financing of extended producer responsibility schemes and possible textile waste targets (by 2029).

In the national regulatory framework represented by the National Strategy for the Circular Economy, approved by Ministerial Decree n. 259 of 24 June 2022, which highlights the role of extended producer responsibility (EPR) to achieve strategic “circular” supply chains and in the light of the general principles of Extended Producer responsibility, governed by art. 178-bis and 178-ter and 237 of Legislative Decree No. n. 152/2006, as amended (178-bis and 237) and introduced (178-ter) by Legislative Decree No. n. 116/2020 (transposing the European directives on circular economy), the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security, MASE, has prepared a draft decree for the implementation of an EPR regime in the textile sector, a responsibility regime currently not provided by any specific regulation.

The draft decree applies to waste resulting from post-consumer textile products placed on the market, with reference to clothing, footwear, accessories, leather goods, home and hospitality textiles. The entities subject to the obligations of Extended Producer Responsibility are those who produce and place on the national market, for the first time, the categories of finished products mentioned above.

In the draft decree specific targets were set for the separate collection of post-consumer textile waste to start to preparation for reuse, recycling and recovery, calculated with respect to the placing on the market of textile products in the previous three years (at least 15% by weight by 2026, at least 25% by weight by 2030, at least 40% by weight by 2035).

Among the most important obligations, introduced by the draft EPR decree and imposed on producers, we highlight the following:

a) financing of separate collection (art. 4, paragraph 2): the producer is required to finance the urban recycling of textile waste, as well as the sorting, preparation for re-use, recycling and recovery of products, in proportion to its market share calculated on the weight of products placed on the market in the calendar year preceding the reference year;

b) management and organization of compliance with the EPR regime (art. 4, paragraph 3): the producer must ensure adequate financial and organizational resources to fulfil the obligations arising from the EPR regime, through the performance of specific tasks, including, for example, to ensure, in particular, the removal of waste and the development and organisation of specific selective collection systems;

c) pouring of the cd. "environmental contribution" (art. 4, paragraphs 4-9), the Producer is required to pay an economic contribution, called "environmental contribution", intended to cover the costs of collection, sorting, treatment, preparation for reuse, recycling and recovery of textile waste as well as to finance prevention, communication, environmental education, research and innovation activities to improve the sustainability of the fashion sector; the amount of the environmental contribution must be adequate, sufficient and relevant to the objectives pursued; the environmental contribution is due for the following product categories: clothing, footwear, clothing accessories, leather goods, household textiles. These categories have been classified either by the ATECO code, referred to the production activities from which the products are generated, or by the Prodcom codes that refer specifically to the nature of the product.

d) Eco-design and prevention (art. 6): the producer must promote eco-design throughout the entire life cycle of the product, according to EU legislation, promoting the reduction of the environmental impact of its products through actions such as: accurate reporting on sustainability and circularity impacts, preparation of the digital product passport, etc.;

e) re-use and reuse (art. 7): the producer shall take measures to encourage re-use and repair of used textile products, for example by promoting sales activities in c.d. second hand markets, including digital platforms, the organisation of awareness campaigns, the dissemination of national and local repair shop networks in order to develop circular models which represent a cost-effective alternative to fast fashion;

f) consumer information and transparency (art. 15): the producer must ensure transparency towards consumers and end-users, informing them about the technical characteristics of each product, waste prevention measures, reuse centres etc.

The producer is required to comply with the obligations of the EPR regime through the constitution of the cd. management systems, which can be set up either collectively, then in the form of consortia with other producers, or individually.

When the decree on Extended Producer Responsibility is adopted, the management systems should be recognised by the MASE.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE ECONOMIC IMPACT OF REGULATIONS

The economic dimension is a decisive factor in shaping the circular transition, influencing how quickly and effectively businesses can adapt to new sustainability frameworks. While regulatory measures provide the necessary legal foundations, their impact depends largely on whether companies perceive circular practices as economically viable and strategically beneficial. For many firms—particularly small and medium-sized enterprises—the transition from a linear “take-make-dispose” model to a circular one still entails significant financial risks, including high upfront costs, uncertain returns on investment, and limited demand for secondary materials.

To address these challenges, governments and institutions at European, national, and regional levels have introduced a wide range of economic instruments designed to lower costs, reduce risks, and create market incentives for circular practices. These include direct funding programs, tax credits, and subsidies, as well as long-term mechanisms such as Green Public Procurement and Extended Producer Responsibility schemes. Together, these policies are reshaping industry dynamics by rewarding durability, reparability, and resource efficiency, while encouraging investment in new business models and circular value chains.

Evidence from across Europe shows that when economic measures are effectively designed and implemented, they can transform barriers into opportunities—stimulating innovation, attracting private investment, and creating competitive advantages for early adopters. Successful initiatives in sectors such as textiles, construction, manufacturing, and electronics demonstrate that aligning financial incentives with regulatory frameworks not only reduces environmental impact but also generates tangible economic and social benefits, from cost savings and new markets to job creation and regional development.

4.1 ECONOMIC BARRIERS TO CIRCULAR TRANSITION

Transitioning from a linear “take-make-dispose” model to a circular economy (CE) model poses significant economic challenges for businesses. From the perspective of companies—especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)—the circular transition often requires substantial upfront costs and strategic changes that can be difficult to justify in the short term. Despite the long-term efficiency gains and sustainability benefits, firms frequently encounter immediate financial and market barriers that hinder the adoption of circular practices. Key economic barriers identified include high initial investment requirements, difficulties achieving economies of scale, limited market demand for secondary materials and circular products, insufficient access to financing, and regulatory uncertainty. These factors can combine to make circular business models appear riskier or less profitable than linear models in the near term, slowing the pace of change.

High Initial Investment Costs and Long ROI

Implementing circular economy strategies typically involves significant initial expenditures. Businesses may need to invest in new technologies (e.g. advanced recycling or remanufacturing equipment), redesign products for circularity, adapt production processes, or establish reverse logistics systems. These changes entail high upfront capital costs, which can be prohibitive for many firms, particularly SMEs with limited financial resources. For example, installing sorting and recycling facilities or retooling a manufacturing line for recycled inputs can require substantial funding at the outset. Moreover, the return on investment (ROI) for circular initiatives often materializes over a longer horizon than most conventional projects [20]. Cost savings from resource efficiency or revenue from secondary materials may take years to offset the initial expense. This long payback period can deter companies under pressure to deliver short-term profits. Indeed, multiple studies have found that high initial investment costs coupled with uncertain or low immediate returns are among the most critical barriers to CE adoption. In practice, this means that even firms motivated to become more circular may postpone or scale back plans due to the sheer upfront cost and the risk that the financial benefits will not be realized for some time.

Lack of Economies of Scale

Many circular economy activities have not yet achieved the scale needed to be cost-competitive with linear systems. In early stages of a circular transition, companies often operate pilots or niche projects (for instance, a small-scale recycling program or a limited product take-back scheme) that do not benefit from volume efficiencies. Without economies of scale, unit costs for circular products or recycled materials remain relatively high, making them less attractive in the marketplace. For example, collecting and processing used products (reverse logistics) can be far more expensive on a small scale: one analysis notes that the “first-mile” reverse logistics of taking back products from consumers lacks scale and can drive costs through the roof [21]. Traditional linear supply chains have matured over decades to maximize efficiency, whereas circular supply chains (for reverse flows of materials) are still developing and often fragmented. A “critical mass” of circular activity is needed to reduce costs but achieving that scale is itself difficult when costs are high. This creates a structural paradox for firms: achieving cost-efficiency through economies of scale requires widespread adoption and infrastructure, yet such scale is difficult to attain precisely because the initial unit costs remain prohibitively high in the absence of that very scale. This barrier is evident in sectors like plastics recycling, where many facilities need a high quantity of waste material to operate profitably; in the interim, smaller operators struggle to compete with the low cost of producing new plastics. Italian stakeholders have also pointed to the lack of critical scale for circular business ventures as a major hurdle, noting that many circular projects cannot attract investment or achieve viability without larger volumes and market participation [22]. In

short, individual firms (particularly SMEs) may find that they alone cannot generate sufficient scale to drive down costs, indicating a need for collaborative approaches or external support to build larger circular value chains.

A promising approach to overcoming the lack of economies of scale is the development of industrial symbiosis networks, where companies collaborate to share resources, waste streams, and logistics infrastructure. These collaborative systems allow firms—especially SMEs—to collectively achieve volume efficiencies and reduce the costs of circular operations. In Italy, national initiatives promoted by ENEA have demonstrated how regional symbiosis hubs can help scale up reverse logistics and material recovery systems in a cost-effective manner [23].

Limited Market Demand for Secondary Materials and Circular Products

Another economic barrier is the relative weakness of market demand for recycled materials and circular products. In many cases, virgin materials and linear products still enjoy cost advantages or entrenched consumer preferences. Recycled or remanufactured materials may be more expensive or perceived as lower quality, reducing their market appeal. This means companies investing in circular practices face uncertainty about revenue: if customers do not purchase recycled-content products or accept refurbished goods, the business case for circularity falters. For instance, a manufacturer considering the use of recycled plastic or textile fibres must contend with the possibility that clients might prefer cheaper “new” materials, especially if there is no regulatory mandate or market incentive to choose recycled. As a result, many firms see little immediate financial reward for switching to secondary materials. The market for secondary raw materials is often underdeveloped, leading to insufficient demand and lower prices for recycled outputs. A recent analysis highlights that without robust demand signals (such as requirements for recycled content or strong green consumer preferences), businesses may find it more profitable to continue using virgin resources. This issue is evident in sectors like construction, where developers may opt for new building materials because reclaimed or recycled options are not readily accepted or are available only in limited quantities. In the textile industry, to give another example, using recycled fabrics or running clothing take-back programs can be costly, and consumer demand for second-hand or recycled fashion, while growing, is not yet mainstream enough to offset those costs. Companies in the textile sector report that cheap, fast-fashion garments made of virgin materials still flood the market, undercutting circular business models [24] (24). Overcoming this demand gap is crucial: without end-market pull, even well-intentioned circular initiatives struggle to sustain themselves economically.

Insufficient Access to Financing

Another challenge for companies, is the difficulty many of them face in securing financing for circular economy projects. Even when a firm is committed to circular innovation, it may lack the internal capital and find that external financiers are reluctant to fund novel circular business

models. Traditional lenders might view circular projects—such as setting up a remanufacturing line or a product-as-a-service model—as high-risk, with unproven cash flows or collateral, and thus charge high interest or refuse credit. SMEs in particular encounter this barrier, as they often do not have large asset bases to borrow against or dedicated sustainability funds at their disposal. A European survey of municipalities and local stakeholders (reflecting the business environment in their regions) found that “insufficient or difficult-to-access financial resources” are a core barrier to circular economy initiatives, often coupled with high perceived financial risks [22]. In practice, this means companies struggle to obtain loans, attract investors, or use public funding schemes to cover the substantial upfront costs of circular transition. For example, a small manufacturing company might see an opportunity to recycle its waste or to develop a new circular product line, but if it cannot secure affordable financing, that opportunity remains theoretical. The lack of tailored financial instruments for circular economy projects (such as dedicated investment funds, green loans, or credit guarantee schemes) has been noted as a gap. Where financing is available, it may come with burdensome administrative requirements that SMEs find hard to meet. This barrier reinforces the others: high upfront costs and long ROI are much harder to bear without accessible financing or subsidies. Thus, improving access to finance is critical to enable businesses to invest in circular solutions despite short-term profitability concerns.

Regulatory Uncertainty and Complexity

Uncertainty in the regulatory environment can pose a significant economic barrier to circular transition. Businesses make long-term investment decisions based on expected rules and incentives; if the policy framework is unclear, inconsistent across regions, or subject to frequent change, companies may delay or forgo circular investments. In the EU context, firms have cited concerns about how future regulations (or the lack thereof) might affect the profitability of circular ventures. For example, uncertainty around definitions of “waste” vs. “product” can deter companies from investing in technologies to convert waste into resources, since a lack of clear end-of-waste criteria creates legal and market risks. Confusing or shifting regulations can thus translate into financial risk for companies. Local administrations in Italy note that confusing regulatory changes discourage the use and reuse of by-products [22], which in turn discourages private investment in circular reuse pathways. A prominent case highlighting regulatory uncertainty is in the plastics recycling sector: recent interviews with industry leaders in Europe revealed that policy uncertainty about the EU’s strategy for plastics (e.g., the priority given to recycling vs. other treatments) has put planned recycling investments on hold. Investors are hesitant to fund new advanced recycling plants if they are unsure how forthcoming regulations (such as recycled content mandates, import rules, or chemical recycling approvals) will evolve. Similarly, in the manufacturing sector, companies redesigning products for circularity (e.g., for easier disassembly or recycling) need regulatory clarity on standards and liability. If different EU countries interpret waste and product regulations inconsistently, it creates a fragmented market

that undermines economies of scale for circular products. In summary, when regulations are unpredictable or overly complex, businesses perceive greater risk and cost in pursuing circular models. A stable, coherent policy landscape is essential to give companies confidence that if they invest in circular solutions now, the “rules of the game” will continue to support and reward those choices in the future.

4.1.1 Sectoral Examples

The above economic barriers manifest with particular intensity in certain industries, offering insights into the sector-specific challenges of the circular transition. In the textiles sector, which is a major industry in the European Union and Italy, companies face high costs to collect, sort, and recycle post-consumer textiles. The technology for fibre-to-fibre recycling is still developing, often requiring manual sorting of fabrics and advanced processing for material recovery. These processes are expensive, and currently only a small fraction of textile material is recycled into new textiles – globally, estimates suggest just 0.3% of material inputs in the textile industry come from closed-loop recycling [23]. Economic barriers here include the low price of new clothing (driven by globalized production and inexpensive raw materials) which makes recycled textiles comparatively costly, as well as the lack of a robust market for recycled fibres. The Prato textile district in Italy, a historic hub for wool recycling, exemplifies how economic and regulatory barriers can limit circular transition even in regions with long-standing circular practices. While Prato produces around 3% of EU textiles and has a legacy of reusing wool scraps, local SMEs increasingly face challenges such as high investment costs, volatile demand for recycled products, and limited access to advanced recycling infrastructure [25].

In the construction and demolition sector, the circular economy principles entail reusing materials (like steel beams, bricks, windows) and recycling aggregates from demolished structures. However, economic barriers in construction include the high labour and logistic costs of material recovery and the fact that new raw materials (cement, virgin aggregates, etc.) are often readily available at low cost. Contractors may find that carefully deconstructing a building to salvage materials is far more time-consuming and expensive than a traditional demolition, and the salvaged materials might not have a guaranteed buyer or may fetch low prices. Even though Europe has a strong recycling rate for construction waste in aggregate (due to backfilling and low-grade uses), high-value reuse and recycling are lagging because of cost and demand constraints. For instance, using recycled aggregates in new concrete is technically feasible but if regulations do not mandate it, builders often prefer virgin aggregates which are cheaper and have uniform quality. In Italy, some regional initiatives promote the reuse of construction components (for example, using recovered stones or tiles in new projects), but widespread adoption will require adjusting cost structures and building standards to favor secondary materials.

Lastly, in mainstream manufacturing sectors like electronics and automotive, companies attempting circular models (e.g. product-service systems, remanufacturing, using recycled inputs) encounter a mix of economic, technical, and market barriers. For example, in the electronics industry, manufacturers seeking to adopt circular models—such as remanufacturing devices or incorporating recycled plastics—continue to face significant cost barriers. A recent study highlights that reverse logistics, especially activities like collection from consumers, transportation, and manual disassembly, remains substantially costlier than traditional linear logistics due to low throughput and the absence of automated processing systems [26]. Moreover, consumer perceptions further complicate the economic viability of circular models. Research on the automotive remanufacturing sector—whose challenges mirror those in electronics—reveals that customers often perceive remanufactured products as inferior, leading to discounted resale prices and placing downward pressure on revenues [27]. These economic and market dynamics mean that, without supporting policies or incentives, even technically feasible circular business models can become financially unviable. Thus, despite technological advancements, economic barriers in remanufacturing electronics persist due to high processing costs and consumer valuation gaps, underscoring the need for targeted interventions—such as subsidies, design incentives, or consumer awareness campaigns—to enable sustainable circular transitions in this sector.

In conclusion, economic barriers to circular transition are significant but not insurmountable. They require a concerted response: companies need supportive ecosystems to make circular models viable, and policymakers have the tools to provide that support. By lowering financial barriers, building markets, and setting clear rules, regulatory policy can drive the circular economy forward despite the economic challenges. This not only helps businesses (by unlocking new opportunities and increasing resilience in the long run) but also ensures that the societal benefits of a circular economy – resource security, innovation, and reduced environmental impact – can be realized. The following section (4.2) will delve into the positive incentives and economic instruments that complement this effort, showing how the right mix of policies can transform the barriers identified above into drivers of a circular and sustainable industrial transformation.

4.2 ECONOMIC INCENTIVES FOR CIRCULAR TRANSITION

Effective economic incentives are crucial for accelerating the adoption of CE models, especially among businesses and SMEs that often face upfront costs and financial risks. By offsetting costs and creating market advantages for circular practices, these incentives complement regulatory measures and help overcome economic barriers. The European Union and Italy have deployed a mix of short-term financial supports (grants, subsidies, tax credits) and long-term market-based instruments (green public procurement, extended producer responsibility, innovation programs) to encourage companies to invest in circular solutions. This section provides an overview of key

incentive mechanisms at the EU and Italian national/regional levels, illustrating how they reduce financial risk, spur innovation, and scale up circular business models.

4.2.1 Short-Term Financial Incentives: Grants, Subsidies & Tax Credits

One of the most direct ways to support the circular transition is through funding programs that provide grants, subsidized loans, or tax relief for circular projects. The EU's unprecedented Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) – part of the post-COVID Recovery Plan – dedicates significant resources to green transition, including circular economy initiatives. For example, Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) allocates about €5.27 billion to “sustainable agriculture and circular economy”, funding new waste management infrastructure, recycling facilities, and flagship circular projects [28]. These infusions of capital help de-risk circular business investments by covering a portion of the upfront costs for new technologies, equipment, or process changes. EU cohesion policy and Structural Funds similarly invest in regional circular economy projects, from improving recycling systems to supporting industrial symbiosis and eco-innovation in local SMEs. On the innovation front, the EU's research programs provide substantial grant funding: Horizon Europe, the €95.5 billion R&I framework (2021–2027), supports numerous projects on circular design, materials recovery, and new business models [29]. Many Horizon Europe projects include SME partners or offer dedicated calls (e.g. Up2Circ, CIRCULOOS) to help SMEs pilot circular solutions. Likewise, the LIFE Programme – the EU's environment and climate fund with €5.4 billion for 2021–2027 – has a sub-programme for circular economy and has co-financed hundreds of demonstration projects across Europe [30]. These grants and subsidies directly support innovation (e.g. a manufacturing SME receiving LIFE funding to test a recycled material in production) and lower the financial barrier for companies to experiment with circular practices.

At the national level, Italy and other Member States have introduced complementary financial incentives for circular economy. Under Italy's PNRR (powered by RRF grants and loans), numerous calls and funding schemes have been launched to support businesses in areas like waste recycling, regenerative agriculture, and renewable materials. In addition, Italy has implemented targeted tax credits and bonus schemes to encourage circular practices. For instance, in 2021 Italy introduced a corporate tax credit for using recycled or compostable materials in products and packaging [31]. This incentive, though temporary, aimed to reward manufacturers that incorporate secondary raw materials, effectively reducing their tax burden to balance any higher cost of recycled inputs. Early uptake of such measures has varied, and policymakers have learned that short-lived incentives are less effective – the OECD recommends sustaining these measures over multiple years so that firms can factor them into long-term investment plans. Prolonged and predictable incentives (e.g. multi-year tax credits or guaranteed feed-in tariffs for recycled material use) give businesses greater confidence to invest in new equipment and supply chains. Some incentives have already shown success: Italy's “Transition

4.0” program, while primarily aimed at digitalization, provided enhanced tax credits for innovation projects with environmental benefits, encouraging SMEs to pursue circular product redesign and cleaner production processes. Several Italian regions have also deployed grants to accelerate the circular transition among local firms – for example, Lombardy’s Circular Economy call in 2022 offered over €4 million in grants to consortia of SMEs for developing circular supply chains. These short-term financial instruments – whether EU or national – help mitigate the initial financial risk of circular solutions, making it easier for businesses to try new processes (like remanufacturing or reuse systems) that might not yield immediate profits. By sharing the cost and risk, grants and subsidies enable pilot projects and innovations that can later be scaled up commercially.

4.2.1 Long-Term Market-Based Incentives: GPP, EPR & Innovation Ecosystems

Alongside direct funding, governments are shaping market conditions and price signals to favor circularity over the long run. A key long-term economic incentive to support circular business models is the adoption of Green Public Procurement (GPP) policies. Italy stands out as a frontrunner in this area, having introduced mandatory GPP at the national level since 2016, and further strengthened its enforcement with the new Public Procurement Code in 2023. As discussed in the previous chapter from a legal perspective, this regulatory framework establishes a binding obligation for all public authorities to apply Minimum Environmental Criteria (CAM) in their procurement procedures for goods, services, and public works, thus combining legal enforcement with economic incentives to accelerate the transition towards circular business practices.

These criteria include requirements such as minimum recycled content, product durability, reparability, and the presence of eco-labels or certifications. For instance, the CAM for construction materials (e.g., concrete, steel, asphalt) mandate recycled content thresholds of at least 7–10%, while criteria for furniture, ICT equipment, and catering services promote energy efficiency and low environmental impact. By shaping demand through public contracts, GPP provides a guaranteed market for circular and eco-designed products, enabling companies to recoup investments in sustainability and innovation.

Italy’s GPP framework has led to significant market uptake. In 2019, the value of green public procurement in Italy accounted for approximately 10.4% of GDP, amounting to €186 billion, with around 26% of this linked to construction projects [\[32\]](#).

However, while the regulatory framework is ambitious, several implementation challenges remain, such as inconsistent application across contracting authorities, limited technical capacity, and a lack of monitoring mechanisms.

To enhance the effectiveness of GPP, policy recommendations include: strengthening verification and enforcement systems; increasing minimum environmental thresholds; and offering technical and financial support to SMEs to participate in green tenders. As one of the few

EU countries with mandatory GPP across sectors, Italy offers an important reference model—although further improvements are needed to fully exploit its transformative potential for circular markets. In sum, GPP acts as a long-term incentive by shifting procurement criteria from lowest-price to life-cycle value, thus rewarding sustainability and circularity in a sustained manner.

Another cornerstone of long-term circular incentives is Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes. EPR is a policy approach that makes producers financially (and sometimes operationally) responsible for the end-of-life of the products they put on the market. In practice, EPR in the EU requires producers to finance the collection, recycling, and proper disposal of waste from products like packaging, electronics, batteries, and more. This creates an economic incentive for producers to design products that last longer or are easier to recycle, since better design can reduce the fees, they must pay. Well-designed EPR schemes use modulated fees – for example, a packaging producer might pay a lower fee per ton if their packaging is easily recyclable or contains higher recycled content. As highlighted in the previous chapter from a legal standpoint, EPR is grounded in binding regulatory frameworks that define the scope of producer obligations, the governance of collection and recycling systems, and the enforcement mechanisms. This legal foundation ensures that the economic responsibility assigned to producers is not merely voluntary but mandatory, thereby aligning legal compliance with market-based incentives to drive circularity.

The EU has increasingly mandated EPR across various waste streams as a way to internalize environmental costs and drive circular design. Italy introduced the EPR principle in its legislation in 2006 and has operational EPR consortia for packaging (CONAI), electronics (RAEE), batteries, tires, and more. These schemes have raised recycling rates significantly – for instance, thanks in part to EPR, over 64% of packaging waste in Europe was already being recycled by 2018, up from roughly half in the early 2000s [33]. In the electronics sector, the WEEE Directive (an EU EPR law) helped increase documented e-waste collection in the EU from 3.8 million tonnes in 2010 to about 5.6 million tonnes in 2021, a notable growth in recycling output [34]. These outcomes demonstrate how shifting end-of-life costs onto producers creates a continuous financial driver for improving product circularity. EPR programs also often invest in consumer awareness (e.g. labelling, take-back campaigns) and in recycling infrastructure, reducing the burden on municipalities. SMEs benefit from EPR because it levels the playing field – all producers fund the system, so eco-friendly startups are not at a cost disadvantage against competitors who might otherwise pollute “for free.” Moreover, the collective nature of many EPR schemes (producers join consortia) means even smaller companies can manage their recycling obligations efficiently.

New EPR schemes are now emerging for additional sectors: as of 2025, Italy has officially implemented an Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) scheme for textiles, aligning with EU-wide initiatives under the Circular Economy Action Plan. This marks a significant shift in the regulatory landscape: producers are now financially and operationally responsible for managing the end-of-life phase of textile products, including their collection, sorting, and recycling.

The adoption of EPR in the textile sector addresses a longstanding gap—until recently, there was no systematic take-back infrastructure for clothing and household textiles. The new framework allocates dedicated funding to support the development of reverse logistics systems, textile sorting centres, and recycling technologies. It also introduces eco-modulation mechanisms that link producer fees to product design attributes such as durability, reparability, and recyclability. This change is already reshaping industry dynamics. Large brands are increasingly adopting circular strategies, such as using mono-material fabrics, integrating recycled fibres, and incentivizing consumers through take-back programs. At the same time, EPR is fostering the emergence of a supporting ecosystem, including SMEs specializing in fibre recovery, logistics innovation, and mechanical and chemical recycling. These developments are not only enhancing material recovery rates but also generating new employment opportunities and regional circular value chains.

Beyond procurement and producer responsibility, public innovation and investment programs play a central role in scaling up the circular economy in the EU and Italy. The European Investment Bank (EIB) and national promotional banks such as Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP) have significantly expanded financing for circular projects. Through the Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE), over €8.9 billion has been invested across Europe in sectors like plastics recycling and recycled materials manufacturing. These institutions offer preferential loans, guarantees, and equity tailored to circular ventures, helping de-risk projects and attract private capital [35]. On the R&D side, the EU's Horizon Europe program (2021–2027) continues to fund pilot projects on circular solutions in key sectors including textiles, construction, and electronics. Between 2016 and 2020, more than €10 billion was allocated through Horizon 2020, LIFE, cohesion funds, and other EU instruments, with additional funding now being channelled via the Recovery and Resilience Facility [36].

All of these efforts recognize that innovation is a long-term driver of the circular transition. Today's subsidy for a prototype can lead to tomorrow's self-sustaining circular business. By continuously funding early-stage research, pilot lines and skill-building, public programs reduce the risk for private investors and help new circular solutions reach the market. In fact, policymakers acknowledge that public funds alone cannot cover all needs – the ultimate goal is to leverage private capital alongside public support. Robust public investment ecosystems in the EU and Italy are ensuring that cutting-edge circular technologies keep evolving, so that businesses can adopt new circular models with greater confidence and at lower financial risk.

4.2.3 Sector-Specific Examples of Incentives

Economic incentives have already shown positive results across various industries, illustrating their practical impact:

- Textiles and Fashion: The implementation of textile EPR across Europe is already producing measurable results. As discussed in the legal analysis of the previous section,

the recent EU regulatory framework has laid the foundations for mandatory collection and recycling schemes, creating the conditions for economic measures to take hold. France's long-established scheme has helped finance a national reuse and recycling system, achieving over 38% recovery of textile waste. Italy's rollout is following a similar trajectory, with regional ecosystems—such as the Prato district—capitalizing on public funding to scale up fibre recovery, mechanical recycling, and wool reprocessing. At the EU level, complementary instruments such as Horizon Europe and LIFE continue to fund technologies that enhance EPR effectiveness, including blended-fibre separation and material tracking systems. These combined incentives are strengthening the sector's capacity for circular transformation.

- **Construction and Demolition:** Construction is a resource-intensive sector now being steered toward circularity through both regulatory incentives and financial support. As underlined in the preceding legal chapter, the evolution of EU and national procurement rules has progressively embedded environmental requirements into construction practices. Green Public Procurement is a key lever – Italy's CAM criteria for construction require using recycled materials (e.g. recycled aggregate in road base layers and recycled gypsum in drywall), which has stimulated a market for construction and demolition (C&D) waste recycling. To complement this, some countries impose virgin material taxes that make reclaimed materials more price competitive. A notable example is the UK's Aggregates Levy, a tax on freshly quarried stone and gravel, which was explicitly designed to encourage recycling of aggregates and reduce environmental impacts of quarrying. Introduced in 2002, this levy (approximately £2 per tonne) helped the UK achieve one of the highest C&D waste recovery rates in Europe – over 90% of construction waste is now recovered or recycled [37]. On the funding side, the EU's LIFE programme has co-funded projects demonstrating circular construction practices (such as reusing building components) and some regional authorities offer grants for green building innovations. The result is a growing number of pilot buildings constructed with high recycled content or modular designs for disassembly, proving that financial and policy incentives can shift construction firms towards circular approaches.
- **Manufacturing and Consumer Goods:** In manufacturing sectors (from packaging to electronics), fiscal incentives and R&D programs have accelerated the adoption of circular practices. For instance, Italy's 2021 tax credit for recycled plastics in packaging gave many companies a direct financial reason to replace virgin plastic with recycled resins. While the incentive was time-limited, some packaging producers seized the opportunity to experiment with higher recycled content, gaining experience that aligned with upcoming EU requirements (the EU is introducing mandatory recycled content targets for plastic bottles and other packaging) [31].

- Electronics: In the electronics sector, EPR schemes have become a key driver of innovation in product end-of-life management. Producer responsibility fees are increasingly being reinvested in systems that improve the collection, dismantling, and recycling of electronic waste (WEEE). Some schemes even offer consumer-facing incentives—such as take-back rebates or discounts on new purchases—encouraging the return of end-of-life devices. Italy's WEEE collection rates have steadily improved over the past decade. Thanks to coordinated efforts by the Centro di Coordinamento RAEE, producers have consistently expanded public take-back networks, upgraded recycling infrastructure using EPR revenues, and introduced eco-modulated fees to reward more recyclable product designs. These efforts have led to improved material recovery quality and higher recycling efficiency. Moreover, collaboration among manufacturers, recyclers, and standardization bodies is fostering design-for-recycling practices and ensuring more consistent dismantling protocols across the supply chain [38].

4.3 BEST PRACTICES AND INTERNATIONAL CASE STUDIES

This section highlights outstanding examples of circular economy policy implementation in Europe – including Italian initiatives – and company-level success stories. These cases demonstrate how well-designed regulations and incentives can drive circular transformation across sectors, leading to tangible outcomes such as higher recycling rates, cost savings, new markets, and job creation. Lessons from these experiences can inform future Italian and EU policy design.

4.3.1 National and Regional Initiatives in Europe Driving Circularity

Many European countries have established comprehensive circular economy strategies or action plans in recent years. As of 2024, 24 out of 27 EU Member States have adopted a national circular economy policy or roadmap, underlining a broad commitment to move beyond linear “take-make-dispose” models. Early leaders like Finland (the first national CE roadmap in 2016) and the Netherlands (vision of a fully circular economy by 2050) set ambitious agendas that others have followed. The Netherlands' strategic push has already fostered an estimated 85,000 circular economy initiatives involving about 420,000 jobs (roughly 4% of all Dutch jobs) – a strong indication that circularity can go hand-in-hand with economic opportunity. In France, the government enacted a far-reaching Anti-Waste Law (loi AGEC) in 2020 that introduced measures such as phasing out single-use plastics by 2040, mandating reparability scores on appliances, expanding EPR schemes to new products, and banning the destruction of unsold goods [39]. This comprehensive regulatory package aims to cut waste generation (e.g. 50% reduction in landfill by 2025 and 100% recycled plastic by 2025) and spur innovation in reuse and repair. While still being implemented, France's law has been lauded as a model; for instance, France was the first country to ban supermarkets from discarding unsold food (2016), resulting in supermarkets now

donating edible surplus to charities. As a result, millions more free meals are expected to be delivered to people in need each year, turning waste prevention into a social benefit.

Other national policies have targeted specific waste streams with great success. Deposit-return systems (DRS) for beverage containers are a prime example of an incentive-based regulatory measure that achieves high recycling rates. Lithuania's DRS, introduced in 2016, led to a dramatic rise in bottle and can returns – recycling rates jumped from 34% to 74% in the first year, and reached 91.9% by the second year. Today, Lithuania's system consistently collects and recycles about 92% of all beverage containers placed on the market, exceeding EU targets for 2025 [40]. This success, achieved via a modest €0.10 deposit, demonstrates how economic incentives can motivate consumers and producers to close material loops. Likewise, Italy's ban on lightweight single-use plastic shopping bags (enacted in 2011, the first such ban in the EU) combined regulation with market innovation. The law prohibited traditional plastic carrier bags and allowed only compostable bioplastic bags, spurring the growth of Italy's bioplastics sector. Within two years, Italy saw a 33% drop in plastic bag consumption (from 145,000 tons in 2010 to 97,000 tons in 2012) and its domestic producers of compostable bags expanded operations, adding an estimated 500 new jobs to meet demand. This policy not only reduced litter and marine pollution but also created an industrial advantage in compostable materials – a clear example of regulation enabling circular innovation.

At sub-national levels, cities and regions across Europe have been important testbeds for circular economy initiatives. For example, the town of Capannori in Tuscany – the first Italian city to pursue a “Zero Waste” strategy – launched rigorous separate collection and reuse programs starting in 2007. Over 15 years, Capannori's community-driven approach dramatically reduced waste: by 2022 its separate collection rate exceeded 81% and residual waste fell to only ~59 kg per person (about 60% below the national average). Capannori's success helped spark a national Zero Waste movement, and by late 2023 over 330 Italian municipalities (encompassing 7.2 million residents) had formally committed to zero-waste goals aimed at waste reduction, repair, and reuse [22]. Regional governments are also innovating. Emilia-Romagna, for instance, was the first region to embed circular economy principles in law – its Regional Law 16/2015 set ambitious targets for 2020, including a 20–25% cut in per-capita waste generation, 73% separate collection, and 70% recycling, alongside strict landfill diversion measures. To reach these goals, the region introduced incentives (funded partly by landfill taxes) to reward high-performing municipalities and discourage disposal [31]. Lombardy likewise approved a Circular Economy Roadmap in 2020 to guide research collaborations, industrial symbiosis projects, and green public procurement initiatives supporting a regional circular transition. These local and regional initiatives complement national policies by demonstrating on-the-ground circular economy gains – from higher recycling rates and cleaner environments to concrete financial benefits [41].

Empirical studies confirm that municipalities adopting Zero Waste strategies achieve significantly better recycling performance (about 4% higher separate collection rates) and

generate 20–26 kg less unsorted waste per capita. In the city of Parma, for example, shifting to a zero-waste, door-to-door collection system not only boosted recycling but also reduced annual waste management costs by roughly €450,000, mainly through savings on landfill disposal fees. Such examples illustrate how local actions can translate circular economy principles into tangible environmental and economic benefits at the community level.

4.3.2 Sector and Company-Level Case Studies of Circular Transition

On the industry front, numerous companies and industrial clusters in Europe have pioneered circular business models, frequently supported by enabling policies or public-private partnerships.

A standout example in the textile sector is Italy's Prato textile district, often heralded as the cradle of textile recycling in Europe. Prato's cluster of over 7,000 firms has for decades specialized in collecting old garments (especially wool) and regenerating them into high-quality yarns and fabrics. By combining its deep-rooted industrial heritage with targeted innovation, Prato has emerged as a leading hub for circular textiles in Europe. The district's textile firms are pioneers in the mechanical recycling of wool and other fibres; a practice now fully embedded in local production systems. As of 2018, companies in Prato recycled over 140,000 tonnes of textile waste annually, representing 15% of global textile recycling and supplying approximately 3% of Europe's overall textile production. This model demonstrates how circularity can be not only environmentally beneficial but also economically viable, underpinning a high value reclaimed wool industry that is globally competitive [42]. Prato's commitment to circularity also extends to industrial water reuse. The district was the first in Italy to implement a closed-loop water cycle in the dyeing sector, reducing freshwater withdrawals through the reuse of treated wastewater. By 2005, this system enabled the reuse of more than 5 million cubic meters of water annually. The transition was supported by a national policy on differential water tariffs, which imposed higher fees for freshwater use and incentivized recycled water use—prompting firms to invest in treatment and recycling infrastructure. This case illustrates how regulatory and economic incentives can work together to accelerate circular transitions in traditional manufacturing contexts.

In the automotive manufacturing sector, a recent success story comes from Swedish carmaker Volvo, which has embraced circularity through an expanding remanufacturing program. Volvo now remanufactures 36 types of vehicle components (engines, gearboxes, turbochargers, clutches, etc.), an approach that dramatically cuts resource use and emissions. Each remanufactured part uses roughly 85% less raw material and 80% less energy than producing a new part, and in 2022 alone Volvo's remanufacturing of over 33,000 parts avoided more than 4,800 tonnes of CO₂ emissions. This circular model also makes business sense: Volvo estimates it will save about SEK 1 billion (≈€90 million) in costs by 2025 through such initiatives, underscoring that sustainability and profitability can go hand-in-hand. Spurred by such successes, other

European automakers are scaling up their own circular practices. In 2023, Stellantis opened a new 73,000 m² *Circular Economy Hub* in Italy dedicated to reconditioning and remanufacturing used parts (from engines and gearboxes to EV batteries), with a goal of processing 50,000 remanufactured components by 2025 (and 150,000 by 2030). Stellantis expects this approach to be highly profitable, projecting its circular economy business unit will generate around €2 billion in revenue by 2030. Importantly, this industry shift is reinforced by policy: the EU's latest proposals on end-of-life vehicles explicitly aim to increase the reuse and remanufacturing of parts and materials in new cars. In combination, strong regulatory push and clear economic logic are driving manufacturers to recover value from “waste” streams and to design products for longer, more sustainable lifecycles [43].

In another example of circular innovation, Aquafil, an Italian materials company, has reinvented its business around regenerating nylon. Through its ECONYL® initiative, Aquafil takes discarded nylon waste – such as fishing nets from the ocean and end-of-life carpets – and chemically recycles it into new nylon yarns for fashion and automotive uses. The process yields “the same quality and performance as virgin nylon” but with dramatically lower environmental footprint. For every 10,000 tons of waste regenerated into ECONYL yarn, roughly 70,000 barrels of crude oil are saved and 65,100 tonnes of CO₂ emissions are avoided, reducing nylon's global warming impact by up to 90% versus conventional production. Supported by EU waste directives and consumer demand for sustainable products, Aquafil's circular model has carved out a growing market – its recycled fibres are now used by major clothing and carpet brands, demonstrating how private eco-innovation (aided by clear regulatory signals on waste and recycling) can achieve both ecological and economic gains.

Even the food and agriculture sector are undergoing a circular transition driven by targeted policy frameworks and business adaptation. A key driver at the EU level is the Farm to Fork Strategy, launched in 2020 as part of the European Green Deal. The strategy sets out concrete goals to reduce food waste by 50% per capita by 2030, improve sustainable food production, and enhance circularity across the agri-food chain [44]. It promotes incentives for food waste prevention, valorisation of by-products, and greater transparency through eco-labelling. These measures aim to reshape both supply and demand dynamics toward more resource-efficient food systems. In Italy, the national implementation of this strategy is supported by legislative tools such as the 2016 “Gadda Law” (Law 166/2016), which simplifies food donation procedures and introduces fiscal benefits for surplus food recovery. This has led to significant increases in donations from supermarkets, restaurants, and food processors, making Italy a reference case for combining waste prevention with social solidarity. Together, EU and national initiatives demonstrate how policy design—linking sustainability goals with regulatory simplification and economic incentives—can accelerate the circular transition in the food sector [44].

It is also worth noting that Italy's overall performance in waste recycling and circular material use is already strong by EU standards, thanks in part to years of aligned policies at EU, national and

local levels. Italy is currently one of Europe's top performers in waste recycling, recycling an estimated 79% of all waste (municipal + industrial) – well above major peers (France 56%, UK 50%, Germany 43%) – and has continuously improved its rates in the last decade. For municipal waste alone, Italy now recycles over 53% (vs an EU average ~49%). This progress is linked to a mix of regulatory pressure (e.g. EU landfill diversion targets, which pushed Italy to drastically cut landfilling) and regional initiatives (like advanced separate collection systems in the north). It reflects how multi-level governance and commitment by both public and private actors can yield concrete circular economy outcomes at scale – from higher recycling rates to new green jobs (the Italian recycling sector's turnover reached €23 billion, about 1% of GDP, supporting thousands of jobs).

4.4 THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE INTERVIEWED COMPANIES

In this regard, it is worth recalling the evidence gathered in the Deliverable 6.4 – III part *Mapping Local Industrial Symbiosis* [45], based on a survey conducted with firms in the NODES territory in collaboration with the University of Turin. The results showed that 74% of respondents considered industrial symbiosis to be feasible, reflecting a strong interest in circular practices among firms. However, significant sectoral differences emerged. The construction industry expressed unanimous confidence in the applicability of IS practices, while a large majority of agrifood companies (82%) also demonstrated strong trust in their feasibility. By contrast, within the textile sector—despite being the most strongly represented—28% of firms still expressed doubts about the practical implementation of such practices.

More broadly, the survey confirmed several aspects already underlined in the literature and in our analysis. Costs and bureaucratic procedures emerged as major deterrents, together with the difficulty of finding suitable partners and suppliers along the circular value chain. Yet, alongside these challenges, a growing number of firms are being driven to experiment with circular models. Respondents recognised the strategic importance of becoming more circular, citing motivations such as resource savings, access to new green markets, and enhanced corporate image. At the same time, they emphasised practical difficulties, particularly the lack of adequate economic incentives to offset the high initial costs of circular projects, and the regulatory complexity of long authorisation processes and uncertainty around what is legally permissible when using recovered materials. Overall, these findings align with the present analysis, suggesting that regulatory frameworks alone are insufficient unless accompanied by targeted economic instruments, collaborative infrastructures, and clearer regulatory guidance. By combining the right elements—policy support, market opportunities, and technical know-how—the circular transition can indeed become a concrete reality for SMEs. Initiatives such as NODES play a crucial role in this direction, fostering collaboration between universities and firms to develop innovative solutions within the territory.

These considerations are consistent with the analysis presented in Confindustria's Second Report on the Circular Economy – *Industrial Strategies and Prospects* [46], which emphasizes that the transition to circularity cannot rely solely on environmental regulation but must also be framed as an industrial policy priority. The report confirms that the priorities identified in 2018 remain highly relevant today to support the circular transition: removing regulatory barriers, fostering circular trade, and strengthening national infrastructure. The report underscores that the circular economy must be understood not only as an environmental imperative but also as a central pillar of industrial policy, intersecting with energy, transport, logistics, infrastructure, and public procurement. It highlights how the Italian industrial system has already accumulated significant know-how through successful practices in areas such as bioeconomy, decarbonization, and transport integration, while at the same time identifying persistent barriers that hinder a full transition. Confindustria stresses that regulatory complexity—especially concerning end-of-waste status and the management of by-products—together with burdensome and lengthy authorization procedures, continues to slow down innovation and discourage investment. The lack of targeted economic instruments for SMEs further limits their ability to undertake circular projects. At the same time, the report points out that circularity offers multiple benefits: environmental protection through waste reduction and resource efficiency, economic advantages linked to lower production costs and enhanced competitiveness, and social gains such as the creation of green jobs and the promotion of a culture of sustainability. Confindustria therefore calls for a regulatory framework that ensures harmonization at the European level, greater legal clarity, and stability over time, while also mobilizing adequate financial resources and leveraging green and circular public procurement as a driver of demand for sustainable products. By strengthening the connection between energy transition policies and circular economy strategies, and by ensuring secure access to critical raw materials through circular practices, the report argues that Italy can consolidate its industrial competitiveness while advancing towards strategic independence.

Taken together, the findings of the NODES survey and the Confindustria Report confirm that the transition to circular economy models is widely recognized as strategically crucial but continues to be constrained by regulatory and economic barriers. Both sources highlight that only through coordinated policies, stable regulatory guidance, and targeted support mechanisms can firms—especially SMEs—be enabled to transform awareness of circularity into concrete industrial practices.

5. POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The transition to a circular economy is increasingly recognized as both an environmental necessity and an economic opportunity. Yet its success depends not only on regulatory ambition but also on the ability of policies to address real-world economic and structural challenges faced by businesses and regions. Building on the evidence and case studies analysed in the previous chapters, this chapter distils the main findings of the research and translates them into concrete policy implications. It identifies the most pressing barriers that hinder circular practices, highlights the incentives and regulatory tools that have proven most effective, and outlines key lessons for policymakers aiming to create an enabling environment for circular innovation. Together, these insights form the basis for targeted recommendations to support a just, competitive, and sustainable circular transition at both the European and national levels.

5.1 MAIN RESULTS OF THE ANALYSIS

The analysis conducted throughout this report highlights both the opportunities and the persistent challenges in advancing the circular economy (CE) across European and Italian contexts. A key finding is that regulatory frameworks, while increasingly comprehensive, remain uneven in their effectiveness, particularly in their ability to address the financial and structural barriers that continue to hinder business participation.

From the perspective of firms—especially small and medium-sized enterprises—the transition from a linear “take–make–dispose” model to a circular one is still associated with high upfront investment costs, long payback periods, and difficulties in securing adequate financing. Limited economies of scale and an underdeveloped market for secondary raw materials further constrain profitability, often making circular practices appear less attractive compared to traditional models. These barriers were confirmed not only through the review of existing literature and international case studies but also through the evidence gathered from the companies interviewed within the NODES project.

At the same time, the research shows that well-designed economic incentives can significantly mitigate these barriers. Instruments such as Green Public Procurement (GPP), Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), and targeted tax credits have proven effective in reducing risks, stimulating investment, and creating stable demand for circular products. The Italian experience with mandatory GPP and the forthcoming EPR scheme for textiles illustrates how regulatory clarity, combined with financial support, can trigger structural changes within entire sectors. Similarly, EU-level funding through programs like LIFE, Horizon Europe, and InvestEU has provided critical support for innovation, infrastructure, and pilot projects, helping companies develop and test circular solutions.

Sector-specific evidence underscores the transformative potential of these measures. In textiles, regional ecosystems such as the Prato district have leveraged public funding and industrial

collaboration to scale fibre recovery and recycling, positioning Italy as a leader in textile circularity. In construction, regulatory requirements to integrate recycled materials—combined with fiscal measures like virgin material levies in other EU countries—demonstrate how policy can reshape markets and normalize circular practices.

International best practices further confirm that aligning regulatory frameworks with financial incentives is essential for success. Countries that have adopted integrated approaches—combining clear legislation, predictable incentive schemes, and robust stakeholder collaboration—achieved higher recycling rates, stronger circular value chains, and increased competitiveness.

Overall, the findings of this report point to a clear conclusion: the transition to a circular economy is feasible and already delivering measurable results, but it requires continuous and coordinated action. Addressing persistent economic barriers, scaling effective incentive mechanisms, and ensuring regulatory clarity and stability are all crucial steps to unlock the full environmental, economic, and social benefits of circularity.

5.2 KEY MESSAGES FOR POLICYMAKERS AND STAKEHOLDERS

Achieving a successful transition to a circular economy requires more than regulatory ambition; it demands targeted strategies that address persistent economic barriers, provide effective incentives, and translate lessons from best practices into coherent policy action. The evidence presented in previous chapters has shown that while circular business models can deliver significant environmental and economic benefits, they often face structural obstacles such as high upfront costs, insufficient access to finance, limited economies of scale, and uncertain market demand for secondary materials. Without deliberate and well-designed interventions, these challenges risk slowing the pace of change and undermining progress toward EU and national circularity targets.

In order to provide actionable guidance, the recommendations in this chapter are structured around three core dimensions, reflecting the analytical framework used in Chapter 4. They first focus on strategies to address the main economic barriers that hinder the uptake of circular models, then examine ways to strengthen and refine incentive mechanisms to accelerate business participation and finally set out principles for designing regulatory policies that ensure clarity, stability, and long-term effectiveness.

Drawing on successful initiatives and lessons learned across Europe and Italy; these guidelines aim to equip policymakers and stakeholders with the tools to create the enabling conditions for circular innovation to flourish. By aligning economic instruments with regulatory measures and ensuring long-term policy stability, governments can de-risk circular investments, stimulate demand for sustainable products, and unlock the full economic, social, and environmental potential of the circular economy.

How to remove the economic barriers to CE?

- 1. Facilitate Access to Finance and Reduce Upfront Costs.** High initial investment costs remain one of the most pressing barriers for companies—especially SMEs—seeking to adopt circular models. Policymakers can mitigate this challenge by creating dedicated funding mechanisms such as grants, low-interest loans, and credit guarantee schemes that reduce risk for businesses. Public investment banks and EU-level instruments, including the InvestEU program and national recovery plans, can provide capital for upgrading equipment, piloting new projects, or launching circular startups. Tax incentives can further strengthen the business case, for example through accelerated depreciation of circular economy equipment or tax credits for companies using recycled materials. Ensuring that SMEs can actually benefit from these instruments is essential: simplifying application processes, streamlining bureaucratic requirements, and increasing outreach and awareness are critical steps to ensure inclusivity and uptake.
- 2. Support Economies of Scale through Collaboration and Infrastructure.** Circular practices often remain more expensive than linear ones due to a lack of economies of scale. To overcome this, policymakers should foster collaboration through industrial symbiosis networks and the development of circular hubs where businesses can share infrastructure for collection, sorting, recycling, and remanufacturing. Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan, for instance, has introduced the concept of “Circular Economy Hubs” to pool expertise and capacity in strategic sectors such as textiles. Aggregating demand across municipalities or industry sectors—such as requiring a minimum share of recycled concrete in public works or bioplastics in packaging—can provide the stable market volume needed to achieve competitive prices. Establishing digital marketplaces for secondary raw materials and material banks in construction can also reduce fragmentation and make reuse and recycling more efficient, lowering costs for businesses and increasing the supply of high-quality secondary materials.
- 3. Stimulate Market Demand for Circular Products.** A major barrier to circularity is the limited demand for products with recycled content or for reused and refurbished goods. Public policy can play a key role in breaking this cycle. Green Public Procurement (GPP) is a particularly powerful tool: by requiring a certain share of recycled content in government purchasing or prioritizing refurbished electronics for public offices, authorities create stable demand signals. Binding recycled content targets, such as those already in place for plastics and batteries at EU level, further reassure businesses that there will be markets for their outputs. Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes can be designed to incentivize eco-design and use of recycled materials through eco-modulated fees that reward circular products. Complementary measures, such as environmental labelling (e.g. Italy's “Made Green in Italy”) and consumer awareness campaigns, can gradually shift

preferences, while fiscal measures like resource taxes or removal of subsidies for virgin resource extraction help internalize environmental benefits into prices—making circular products more competitive.

How to incentivize the transition towards CE?

4. **Ensure Long-Term Stability and Predictability.** One of the most frequent concerns voiced by businesses is the unpredictability of incentive schemes. Incentives that are short-lived or frequently revised reduce investor confidence and discourage long-term planning. To address this, policymakers should design programs with a multi-year horizon, such as tax credits valid for 5–10 years or revolving funds dedicated to circular investments. Even if support levels taper over time, providing clear timelines enables companies to integrate these signals into their business strategies and to undertake circular transitions, which often involve significant upfront investments with longer payback periods.
5. **Increase Transparency and Outreach.** Clear and transparent design of incentive schemes is essential for building trust and ensuring fair access. Policymakers should publish clear eligibility criteria, program objectives, and evaluation processes. Making data public on funded projects and their outcomes—such as material savings, CO₂ reductions, or jobs created—can inspire other businesses to follow suit and provide valuable insights into best practices. Consultation with stakeholders, including industry representatives, SMEs, and civil society, ensures that incentives are well-calibrated to actual market needs and avoid unintended loopholes. Communication efforts should also be proactive: establishing one-stop digital portals (e.g. Italy's [Incentivi.gov](https://www.incentivi.gov.it)), offering guidance documents, and providing assistance through industry associations can significantly increase participation, particularly among SMEs.
6. **Tie Incentives to Measurable Outcomes and Accountability.** For incentives to be truly effective, they must be tied to concrete circular economy outcomes. This requires linking financial support to key metrics, such as the volume of recycled materials used, the share of refurbished products, or the amount of waste reduced. Reporting requirements should be proportional to the size of the support, so as not to overburden SMEs, while still ensuring accountability. Periodic reviews and sunset clauses can help adjust or phase out incentives that do not deliver expected results, while scaling up those that prove most impactful. Verification mechanisms—such as requiring certification of recycled content for tax credits—are equally important to maintain a level playing field and avoid misuse of public funds.
7. **Enhance the dissemination of minimum environmental criteria.** Adoption of ministerial decrees even in sectors currently without reference regulations to improve the dissemination of minimum environmental criteria. This would make it possible to

strengthen the obligation to apply the technical specifications and contractual clauses contained in the minimum environmental criteria even for sectors of activity currently without specific regulation and therefore accessible to anyone. Consideration could also be given to strengthening the regulatory provision in the Public Contracts Code that contracting authorities must take into account minimum environmental criteria also for the definition of contract award criteria. It could be considered to include the obligation to provide in the calls for tenders for the attribution of a reward score for compliance with environmental sustainability criteria in order to induce less virtuous economic operators to invest in the sector to adequately respond to the requests of the public administration regarding sustainable purchasing.

8. **Integrate Incentives into a Coherent Policy Mix.** Isolated fiscal incentives are rarely sufficient to trigger a systemic transition; they are most effective when coordinated with regulatory measures. For example, subsidies for recycled material use work best when paired with minimum recycled content standards, creating both supply- and demand-side momentum. Similarly, combining positive incentives (“carrots”), like grants or innovation subsidies, with corrective measures (“sticks”), such as landfill taxes or levies on virgin materials, creates a balanced policy environment that accelerates change while maintaining fiscal sustainability. A coherent policy mix ensures that different instruments reinforce one another rather than working at cross-purposes.

How to set appropriate CE regulatory policies?

9. **Provide Clear and Harmonized Frameworks.** Regulatory clarity is fundamental for businesses making long-term investments. Policymakers should harmonize definitions and standards across EU and national levels—for example, clarifying what qualifies as a secondary raw material or setting consistent end-of-waste criteria. Streamlining permitting processes for recycling plants and simplifying certification for reused components can reduce administrative burdens without compromising environmental and safety standards. At the same time, aligning national and regional regulations prevents contradictory requirements that add unnecessary compliance costs.
10. **Set Ambitious Targets with Long-Term Certainty.** Experience from leading countries shows that bold, long-term targets create strong signals for the market. The Netherlands’ commitment to full circularity by 2050 and Emilia-Romagna’s ambitious waste reduction and recycling targets are examples of how clear goals encourage investment and innovation. Italy’s ban on lightweight plastic bags, which spurred the growth of the bioplastics industry, illustrates how policy certainty can unleash private investment. Policymakers should therefore set measurable and time-bound targets for waste reduction, recycling, and use of secondary raw materials, embedded in stable long-term

roadmaps.

11. **Foster Public-Private Collaboration and Local Experimentation.** Successful circular transitions often emerge from strong collaboration among governments, businesses, and local communities. The Prato textile cluster, with its longstanding wool recycling tradition, illustrates how local ecosystems can thrive when supported by national policy and coordinated through consortia. City-level initiatives such as Capannori's zero-waste strategy show the power of bottom-up approaches to achieve high recycling rates and reduced costs. Policymakers should support such experimentation through pilots, living labs, and knowledge-sharing networks like the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative, ensuring that local innovations can be scaled nationally or replicated across regions.
12. **Promote financing of local projects for waste management and the provision of punctual waste tariffs.** The collaboration between the Region and local authorities - metropolitan cities, provinces and municipalities - on the one hand and citizens and associations on the other is promoted through multiple actions by the Regional Waste Management Programs. With regard to the actions undertaken by the Lombardy Region, we can mention the projects that can be financed for the creation of product reuse centres, hubs and solidarity emporiums for the devolution of food surpluses. The beneficiaries of the projects are Municipalities, Unions of Municipalities and Mountain Communities. The 2021-2027 ERDF PR Funds are aimed at SMEs and local authorities in support of the adoption of sustainable production models and industrial symbiosis actions, waste production prevention, recycling and reuse. In the Piedmont Region, in implementation of the objectives of the circular economy and with the aim of encouraging the application of the waste hierarchy, in some municipalities – Marentino and Pralormo – starting from 1° January 2024 the punctual waste tariff was adopted; this tariff, in application of the principle "polluter pays", calculates the amount due on the basis of the real production of waste.
13. **Ensure Monitoring and Continuous Improvement.** Robust monitoring is crucial to evaluate the effectiveness of policies and adjust them as needed. Tracking outcomes such as recycling rates, CO₂ emissions avoided, or jobs created helps demonstrate impact and build public and political support for further measures. Italy could consider establishing a dedicated observatory to collect and analyse circular economy data, as envisaged in its new CE strategy. Regular evaluation also helps phase out ineffective measures and refine those that deliver the greatest impact.
14. **Leverage EU Funding and Alignment.** Finally, national strategies should be closely aligned with EU-level initiatives and funding streams to maximize impact and avoid duplication. The Recovery and Resilience Facility (PNRR), Horizon Europe, LIFE, and Cohesion Policy funds offer significant resources for circular infrastructure, innovation,

and regional support. Leveraging these instruments ensures that no region is left behind and that Italian policies are fully consistent with EU Green Deal objectives. By preemptively aligning national legislation with forthcoming EU directives—such as those on plastics, textiles, and electronic waste—Italy can not only comply but also turn adaptation into a competitive advantage.

In conclusion, while the transition to a circular economy is confronted by significant economic barriers, these obstacles are not insurmountable when met with a coherent mix of policies, incentives, and collaborative initiatives. By lowering financial hurdles, building markets for secondary materials, and ensuring regulatory clarity and stability, policymakers can create the supportive ecosystems that businesses—particularly SMEs—need to adopt circular models with confidence. Economic incentives, when well-designed, play a decisive role in this process: short-term measures such as grants and tax credits help firms overcome upfront costs, while long-term instruments like Green Public Procurement and Extended Producer Responsibility reshape market dynamics and reward sustainability.

International and national best practices show that circular transition is not only feasible but economically and socially beneficial when anchored in smart policy design. From large-scale recycling systems to local circular hubs, successful cases across Europe demonstrate how integrating regulatory frameworks with financial support can reduce risks, stimulate innovation, and generate tangible benefits, from cost savings and new green jobs to improved resource security and reduced environmental impact.

For Italy and the EU, the path forward lies in scaling up these proven approaches, refining incentive schemes to be more accessible and predictable, and fostering collaboration across industries, regions, and communities. By aligning ambitious environmental objectives with economic viability, policymakers can unlock the full transformative potential of the circular economy, advancing toward a regenerative model that delivers resilience, competitiveness, and sustainability for present and future generations.

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